

Pyramidellidae (Gastropoda, Heterobranchia, Panpulmonata) from the outer continental shelf and slope off Galicia (NW Spain)

Pyramidellidae (Gastropoda, Heterobranchia, Panpulmonata) de la plataforma continental externa y talud de Galicia (NW de España)

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ABSTRACT

Pyramidellidae were studied from several expeditions off Galicia (NW Spain), conducted between 2002 and 2009, sampling in the depth range 102-3200 m. The family was represented by 54 species belonging to 15 genera, of which only 23 were found with soft parts. Five of the species have been identified with doubt, five more, which could be undescribed species, are identified to the genus level only and one species of the genus *Eulimella* is described as new. Most of the species (33) were found in the continental shelf above 250 m depth and 11 were collected deeper than 1000 m. Most species appeared in low abundance, 18 of them represented by one or two shells, while only 16 species were represented by 10 or more shells. Four species (*Parthenina brattstroemi*, *Pyrgiscus mediocris*, *Turbonilla hamonvillei* and *Eulimella atlantis*) are recorded for the first time in Spanish waters, and 13 more are new to northern Spain.

RESUMEN

Se estudiaron los Pyramidellidae procedentes de varias expediciones frente a Galicia (NO de España), realizadas entre 2002 y 2009, muestreando en el rango de profundidad 102-3200 m. La familia estuvo representada por 54 especies pertenecientes a 15 géneros, de los cuales solo 23 se encontraron con partes blandas. Cinco de las especies se identificaron con dudas, otras 5 que podrían ser especies nuevas para la ciencia, solo se identifican a nivel de género, y una especie del género *Eulimella* se describe como nueva. La mayor parte de las especies (33) se encontraron en la plataforma continental por encima de los 250 m de profundidad y 11 se recolectaron a más de 1000 m de profundidad. La mayor parte de las especies resultaron muy poco abundantes (18 de ellas representadas solo por uno o dos ejemplares), mientras que solo 16 especies estuvieron representadas en las muestras por 10 o más conchas. Cuatro especies se citan por primera vez en aguas españolas

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(*Parthenina brattstroemi*, *Pyrgiscus mediocris*, *Turbonilla hamonvillei* y *Eulimella atlantis*), así como otras 13 nuevas para la Demarcación Noratlántica de aguas españolas.

KEY WORDS: Mollusca, Gastropoda, Panpulmonata, Northwest Spain, systematics, taxonomy.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Mollusca, Gastropoda, Panpulmonata, noroeste de España, sistemática, taxonomía.

INTRODUCTION

The present work continues the study of the gastropods from the continental shelf and slope off the coast of Galicia (NW Spain) carried out by the authors. Previous papers addressed conoidean, rissoidean, seguenzioideans, skeneids and on species of the genus *Calliostoma* (OLIVER *ET AL.*, 2022a, 2022b, 2023, 2024; HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2024). This paper deals with the species of Pyramidellidae.

The Pyramidellidae is a remarkably species-rich family of marine gastropods distributed worldwide, mainly in littoral bottoms. This family comprises nearly 160 accepted genera (WoRMS 2024) and thousands of extant species which are all ectoparasitic, mainly on polychaetes and on other molluscs. Pyramidellids are one of the gastropod groups whose taxonomic position has been the subject of greatest controversy (BIELER, 1992; DINAPOLI, ZINSSMEISTER & KLUSSMANN-KOLB, 2011). Based on morphological characters, some proposals placed Pyramidellidae within the traditional 'Prosobranchia' (e.g. GOLIKOV & STAROBOGATOV, 1975; GOSLINER, 1981; ROBERTSON, 1985), due to their spirally coiled shell into which the entire soft parts are retractable, foot with operculum, and an anteriorly orientated mantle cavity. Other placed pyramidellids within the "Opisthobranchia" due to the possession of a pigmented mantle organ, subepithelial eyes on the median side of the tentacles, simultaneous hermaphroditism and a heterostrophic protoconch (e.g. FRETTER & GRAHAM, 1949; SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1980).

The classic three subclasses scheme is nowadays rejected as artificial, and successive revisionary proposals were initiated by HASZPRUNAR (1985a, 1988) and PONDER & LINDBERG (1997). The concept

of the Heterobranchia, introduced by HASZPRUNAR (1985a, 1988) and broadly accepted as a monophyletic clade, comprised the 'lower Heterobranchia' and the Euthyneura (including the traditional Opisthobranchia and Pulmonata). Since then, the Pyramidellidae were first included into the paraphyletic 'lower Heterobranchia' together with the Architectonicoidea, Omalogyroidea, Rissoelloidea and Valvatoidea, because their members show several plesiomorphic heterobranch characters (HASZPRUNAR, 1985b, 1988; PONDER & WARÉN, 1988, HEALY, 1993, PONDER & LINDBERG, 1997). Later, successive molecular studies introduced new proposals and new groups were placed in the basal heterobranchs, such as Orbitestelloidea, Tjaernoieidae, Cimidae, Rhodopemorpha or Acteonoidea (e.g. JÖRGER *ET AL.*, 2010; WÄGELE *ET AL.*, 2014; WILSON *ET AL.*, 2017; BRENZINGER, SCHRÖDL & KANO, 2021), while pyramidellids were placed closer to pulmonates (GRANDE *ET AL.*, 2004; GRANDE, TEMPLADO & ZARDOYA, 2008; KLUSSMANN-KOLB *ET AL.*, 2008; DINAPOLI & KLUSSMANN-KOLB, 2010; VARNEY *ET AL.*, 2021)). The latter authors showed a close relationship of Glacidorboidea, Amphiboloidea and Pyramidellidae, and the last two taxa were grouped under the name Pylopulmonata by TEASDALE (2017), considered with the level of superorder by (BOUCHET *ET AL.*, 2017 and WoRMS, 2024).

Nowadays, pyramidellids are included within Panpulmonata, name introduced by JÖRGER *ET AL.* (2010) for a clade including Siphonarioidea, Sacoglossa, Glacidorboidea, Amphiboloidea, Pyramidelloidea, Hygrophila, Acochlidia, Stylommatophora, Systelommatophora, Ellobioidea, Otinoidea

and Trimusculoidea, sister to Euopisthobranchia and supported by phylogenomic evidence (KOCOT *ET AL.*, 2013; ZAPATA *ET AL.*, 2014; TEASDALE, 2017; BREZINGER *ET AL.*, 2021). Likewise, KRUG *ET AL.* (2022) introduced the taxa Panpulmonata to include all Panpulmonata but Sacoglossa.

The lack of data regarding soft parts for more than 80% of named genera, and the limited number of taxa included in molecular studies, hinder establishing a familial and subfamilial classification of Pyramidelloidea. This also precludes precise inference of their diversification pattern and driving force behind the enormous species richness (DINAPOLI *ET AL.*, 2011). Phylogenetic relationships within pyramidellids were addressed using morphological (WISE, 1996; SCHANDER, HORI & LUNDBERG, 1999) and molecular data (SCHANDER *ET AL.*, 2003; DINAPOLI *ET AL.*, 2011), however these studies dealt with a limited number of taxa. Previously, PONDER (1987) excluded from Pyramidellidae some species with limpet-like appearances of the shell, which he assigned to the family Amathinidae. Likewise, WARÉN (1995) excluded from Pyramidellidae some genera previously included in this family (*Murchisonella*, *Ebala* and *Henrya*) and proposed the name Ebalidae to include these genera, synonymised with Murchisonellidae by BOUCHET & ROCROI (2005). While first molecular data including Amathinidae proved its sister-group relationship to the Pyramidellidae (WISE, 1996), Murchisonellidae was grouped at the base of the Heterobranchia by DINAPOLI & KLUSSMANN-KOLB (2010), outside of the Euthyneura, not forming a sister group relationship with the Pyramidellidae. Therefore, both Pyramidellidae and Amathinidae make up the superfamily Pyramidelloidea (within the euthyneuran Panpulmonata), while Murchisonellidae is included within the “lower” Heterobranchia (DINAPOLI & KLUSSMANN-KOLB, 2010; WARÉN, 2013). Later, the morphological and molecular analyses of BREZINGER WILSON & SCHRÖDL (2014) and WILSON *ET AL.* (2017), respectively, placed the shelled

Murchisonellidae as sister group of the psammobiotic worm-like Rhodopemorpha introducing the clade name Alломорpha for this basal heterobranch lineage, later named Mesoneura by BREZINGER *ET AL.* (2021) to also include the “skeneimorph” family Tjaernoeciidae.

At present none of the subfamilies or tribes of Pyramidellidae can be justified as a natural, monophyletic group because they are based on conchological characters, such as the profile of the teleoconch, surface sculpture, number of columellar teeth or shape of the protoconch, but these do not seem to represent sufficient criteria to uncover deep evolutionary relationships within the family. DINAPOLI *ET AL.* (2011) pointed out that the extraordinary species richness of Pyramidellidae might be due to their adaptive radiation provided from the host groups (annelids and molluscs) in a vast variety of habitats across wide depths ranges and geographic areas. Unlike the Eulimidae, the other major group of parasitic gastropods, species of the family Pyramidellidae are temporary parasites and exhibit low host specificity. Therefore, pyramidellids might perhaps have diversified because of their capability of using new available hosts and habitats (TAKANO, 2015). Host flexibility seems to be an advantageous evolutionary strategy.

Regarding alpha taxonomy, the species of Pyramidellidae from the eastern Atlantic - Mediterranean and West Africa area have been widely studied. Pyramidellids are also well represented in the fossil record. The extensive works of LANDAU, SILVA & MAYORAL (2011), LANDAU *ET AL.* (2020) and LANDAU & MICALI (2021) on the upper Miocene and Pliocene pyramidellids of western European deposits are outstanding examples.

Despite this extensive bibliography, data on deep-sea pyramidellids is still sparse. In this regard, the works of PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999b) and PEÑAS, ROLÁN & SWINNEN, (2019) on the pyramidellids from some NE Atlantic seamount are noteworthy. Other scattered data on species of this group in

deep bottoms are contained in JEFFREYS (1883), WARÉN (1991), VAN AARTSEN *ET AL.* (1998, 2000), BECK, METZGER & FREIWALD (2006), HOFFMAN, VAN HEUGTEN & LAVALEYE (2009) among others, summarized in SYSOEV (2014).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The material studied comes from several expeditions along the continental shelf and slope off the coast of Galicia (NW Spain), conducted between 2002 and 2009, sampling in the depth range 110-3200 m. Data on these expeditions as well as maps of the sampling stations are provided in previous papers by OLIVER *ET AL.* (2022a, 2022b, 2023, 2024). Sampling methodology and processing of samples were described by PARAPAR & MOREIRA (2009) and in the abovementioned papers.

Benthic samples were taken by the following gears: Naturalist Dredge (DRN), Agassiz trawl (AT), Rock dredge (DRR) and Epibenthic sledge (EBS). Samples were sieved and specimens fixed with ethanol 70% neutralized with borax. Shells retained in sieves of ≥ 2 mm were sorted to high taxonomic levels on the Marine Biological Station of A Graña (University of Santiago de Compostela).

The entire collection of shells and specimens studied has been deposited (preserved dry and in 70% ethanol respectively) at the Museo de Historia Natural of the Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, Galicia (Spain), with the deposit number: MHN USC-10156.

Abbreviations used:

juv: juvenile

sh: empty shell

spc: shell with soft parts

MHN USC: Museo de Historia Natural, University of Santiago de Compostela.

MNCN: Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid.

MNHN: Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris.

Expeditions:

DAI/02: DIVA-Artabria I (2002)

DAI/03: DIVA-Artabria I (2003)

VE/04: Vertidos (2004)

SAR(06-07): Sarridal (2007)

DAII/08: DIVA-Artabria II (2008)

SE/08: A Selva (2008)

FO(09): Forsagal (2009)

RESULTS

The species-rich Pyramidellidae family was represented in the studied samples by about 800 shells (nearly half of them collected alive) belonging to 15 genera and 54 species (Table I), of which only 23 were found with soft parts. Five of the species have been identified with doubt, other five to the de genus level, and one species of the genus *Eulimella* is described below as new for science. All species were collected in the depth range 102-2798 m, but most of them (33 species) were found in the continental shelf above 250 m depth, of which 17 are mainly littoral species represented by very few eroded shells. These last species, considered accidental in the bottoms sampled, are briefly mentioned at the end.

The most abundant species by far was *Odostomia acuta* Jeffreys, 1848, with more than 350 shells and specimens, followed by *Eulimella artabrensis* n. sp. (51), *Megastomia conoidea* (Brocchi, 1814) (46), *Liostomia clavula* (Lovén, 1846) (37) and *Liostomia afzelii* Warén, 1991 (26).

SYSTEMATICS

A complete account of the synonymy of the treated species is beyond the scope of this work and is provided in WoRMS (2024) and also by VAN AARTSEN (1977, 1981, 1987, 1994), SABELLI *ET AL.* (1990-1992), or LANDAU & MICALI (2021). Therefore, we will list only the most recent or noteworthy synonyms and records. The species are addressed bellow in the same order as in the table.

Figure 1. *Tiberia minuscula* (Monterosato, 1880). A-C: shell from DAI/03 EBS-600 (4.65 × 2.4 mm) and details of its columella and umbilicus; D, E: apical view of a protoconch from SE/08 AT-13.
Figura 1. Tiberia minuscula (Monterosato, 1880). A-C: concha de DAI/03 EBS-600 (4,65 × 2,4 mm) y detalles de su columela y ombligo; D, E: vista apical de una protoconcha de SE/08 AT-13.

Class GASTROPODA
Subclass HETEROBRANCHIA Burmeister, 1837
Superfamily PYRAMIDELLOIDEA Gray, 1840
Family PYRAMIDELLIDAE Gray, 1840
Genus *Tiberia* Jeffreys, 1884

Type species by subsequent designation: *Pyramidella minuscula* Monterosato, 1880.

Tiberia minuscula (Monterosato, 1880) (Fig. 1)

Pyramidella minuscula Monterosato, 1880: 224.

Pyramidella mediterranea Monterosato, 1880: 224.

Tiberia mediterranea (Monterosato) – KOBELT (1903: 73-74, pl. 6, figs. 10-11); APPOLLONI *ET AL.* (2018: 69, fig. 27 I-J).

Tiberia octaviana di Geronimo, 1973: 218, fig. 2a-b – PEÑAS & GIRIBET (2003: 183, fig. 21); GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.* (2014: fig. 237, appendix p. 75).

Tiberia minuscula (Monterosato) – PEÑAS, TEMPLADO & MARTÍNEZ (1996: 12, fig. 7); ARDOVINI & COSIGNANI (1999: 79); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2011: 368); SCAPERROTTA, BARTOLINI & BOGI (2013: 101); GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.* (2014: fig. 236, appendix p. 74); PEÑAS, ROLÁN & SWINNEN (2014: 168, fig. 22D-E); APPOLLONI *ET AL.* (2018: 69, fig. 27 M-N).

Tiberia minusculoides van Aartsen, Gittenberger & Goud, 1998: 7, fig. 2.

Table I. Species found, S(L): total number of shells (in brackets, number of shells with soft parts); DR: depth range; SP: species included in the checklist of Mollusca in Spanish waters (GOFAS *ET AL.*, 2017); NO: species recorded on the northern coasts of Spain according to the same checklist; GC: species recorded on the Gulf of Cadiz according to the same checklist; GA: species recorded in Galicia according to TRIGO *ET AL.* (2018); SA: species recorded in the South Azorean Seamount according to PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999) and CABALLERO-HERRERA *ET AL.* (2023a); M: species recorded in the Mediterranean. Species represented by very few eroded shells are included at the end.

Species	S(L)	DR	SP	NO	GA	GC	SA	M
<i>Tiberia minuscula</i>	3	407-516	X			X		X
<i>Megastomia conoidea</i>	46 (22)	102-237	X	X	X	X		X
<i>Brachystomia eulimoides</i>	30 (8)	102-151	X	X	X	X		X
<i>Brachystomia cf. scalaris</i>	11 (1)	110-212	X	X		X		X
<i>Odostomia acuta</i>	350 (260)	102-384	X	X	X	X		X
<i>Odostomia unidentata</i>	7 (2)	110-237	X	X	X	X		X
<i>Odostomia suboblonga</i>	10 (4)	207-1004	X			X		X
<i>Doliella nitens</i>	11 (2)	610-1004	X	X		X		X
<i>Liostomia clavula</i>	37 (26)	110-153	X	X	X			X
<i>Liostomia afzelii</i>	27 (15)	102-153	X					X
<i>Liostomia hansgei</i>	2 (1)	151	X					X
<i>Ondina divisa</i>	6 (1)	110-346	X	X	X			
<i>Pyrgulina stefanis</i>	2	1191-1132	X					X
<i>Spiralina spiralis</i>	9 (7)	110-149	X	X		X		
<i>Parthenina cf. interstincta</i>	10 (1)	102-237	X	X		X		X
<i>Parthenina multicostata</i>	4 (1)	102-111	X	X				X
<i>Parthenina flexuosa</i>	1	802-788	X	X		X	X	X
<i>Parthenina brattstroemi</i>	1	770-842						X
<i>Parthenina aff. brattstroemi</i>	2	788-1191						
<i>Parthenina cf. palazzii</i>	8	102-153	X					X
<i>Eulimella scillae</i>	3	620-1004	X			X		X
<i>Eulimella neoattenuata</i>	3 (2)	709-1150	X				X	X
<i>Eulimella artabrensis</i> n. sp.	51 (13)	102-111						
<i>Eulimella atlantis</i>	2	601-829					X	
<i>Eulimella cerullii</i>	12 (2)	598-610	X		X	X		X
<i>Eulimella</i> sp. 1	7	503-1106						
<i>Eulimella ventricosa</i>	21 (1)	416-1191	X			X		X
<i>Eulimella cf. ataktos</i>	3 (2)	428-616	X					X
<i>Eulimella</i> sp. 2	3 (1)	337-1191						
<i>Turbonilla magnifica</i>	15	566-1191	X	X		X		X
<i>Turbonilla</i> sp. 1	15	102-151						
<i>Turbonilla</i> sp. 2	13 (7)	102-148						
<i>Turbonilla hamonvillei</i>	2	908-2798					X	
<i>Turbonilla multilirata</i>	4	437-610	X					X
<i>Pyrgiscus crenatus</i>	21 (3)	102-236	X			X		X
<i>Pyrgiscus</i> sp.	4 (1)	102-103						
<i>Pyrgiscus mediocris</i>	1	908-1106					X	

Tabla I. Especies encontradas, S(L): número de conchas totales (entre paréntesis, número de conchas con partes blandas); DR: rango de profundidad; SP: especies incluidas en la lista de moluscos en aguas españolas (GOFAS *ET AL.*, 2017); NO: especies citadas en las costas del norte de España según la misma lista; GC: especies citadas en el golfo de Cádiz según la misma lista; GA: especies citadas en Galicia según TRIGO *ET AL.* (2018); SA: especies registradas en los montes submarinos del Sur de las Azores según PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999) y CABALLERO-HERRERA *ET AL.* (2023a); M: especies registradas en el Mediterráneo. Las especies representadas por muy pocas conchas erosionadas se incluyen al final.

Species	S(L)	DR	SP	NO	GA	GC	SA	M
Coastal species represented by few shells								
<i>Megastomia conspicua</i>	2	110-111	X		X	X		X
<i>Brachystomia carrozzai</i>	1	581-566	X	X	X	X		X
<i>Odostomia plicata</i>	1	110-111	X	X	X	X		X
<i>Odostomia turrita</i>	1	110-111	X	X	X	X		X
<i>Odostomia lukisii</i>	1	110-111	X	X	X			X
<i>Odostomella doliolum</i>	1	102-103	X			X		X
<i>Folinella excavata</i>	2	110-111	X	X	X			X
<i>Parthenina monozona</i>	6	102-111	X					X
<i>Parthenina terebellum</i>	1	599-607	X	X	X	X		X
<i>Parthenina decussata</i>	6	110-111	X	X				X
<i>Parthenina indistincta</i>	2	147-150	X	X	X	X		X
<i>Tragula fenestrata</i>	3	102-103	X	X	X	X		X
<i>Eulimella acicula</i>	10	110-111	X	X	X	X		X
<i>Turbonilla lactea</i>	6	110-111	X	X		X		X
<i>Turbonilla</i> sp. 3	2	110-111						
<i>Turbonilla</i> sp. 4	7	102-111	X		X			
<i>Pyrgiscus jeffreysii</i>	3	110-111	X	X	X	X		X

Material examined (3 empty shells in 2 samples): Spain • 1 sh; 43°48.587'N, 08°51.402'W to 43°49.545'N, 08°51.197'W; 598-610 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DAI/03 EBS-600 • 2 sh; 44°07.495'N, 08°46.999'W to 44°07.675'N, 08°45.225'W; 407-416 m; 18 Jul. 2008; SE/08 AT-13.

Type locality: Described from coasts of Algeria, and Sicily (Messina, Palermo and San Vito lo Capo) (APPOLLONI *ET AL.*, 2018).

GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.* (2014) considered *T. mediterranea* Monterosato, 1880 synonym of *T. minuscula*, an opinion reflected by WoRMS (2024). However, APPOLLONI *ET AL.* (2018), who examined the types of marine molluscan taxa described by Monterosato, pointed out that both taxa differ in their shell and apex size. If we follow these last authors, the three shells found in the studied samples (between 400 and 600 m depth) correspond to *T. mediterranea*. Recently, GOFAS *ET AL.* (2021) has recorded in the

Galicia Bank the presence of another possible species of *Tiberia* that differs from *T. minuscula* in having a very thin shell with a markedly keeled last whorl and in being colourless.

Tiberia minuscula is known in circalittoral and upper bathyal bottoms of the Canary and Cape Verde Islands, the Gulf of Cádiz and the western Mediterranean (VAN AARTSEN, GITTEBERGER & GOUD, 1998; PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 2011; PEÑAS *ET AL.*, 2014; UTRILLA *ET AL.*, 2020). It seems to be present in several

Figure 2. *Megastomia conoidea* (Brocchi, 1814). A: shell (2.1 × 1.0 mm) from SE/08 DRN-22; B-D: juvenile shell from VE/04 GA-AT-110, protoconch and microsculpture.

Figura 2. *Megastomia conoidea* (Brocchi, 1814). A: concha (2,1 × 1,0 mm) de SE/08 DRN-22; B-D: concha juvenil de VE/04 GA-AT-110, protoconcha y microescultura.

seamounts and banks of the Alboran Sea (PEÑAS ET AL., 1996; GOFAS ET AL., 2014; CABALLERO-HERRERA ET AL., 2023b). Records from northern Spain are inconsistent; JEFFREYS (1884) reported it

generically from “Bay of Biscay” based on Travailleur 1880 and 1881 samples, but this is not referred in LOCARD (1897). Therefore, our record may be the first positive one for Galicia.

Genus *Megastomia* Monterosato, 1884

Type species by original designation: *Odostomia conspicua* Alder, 1850.

Megastomia conoidea (Brocchi, 1814) (Fig. 2)

Turbo conoideus Brocchi, 1814: 659; pl. 16, fig. 2.

Odostomia conoidea (Brocchi) – MICALI (1983b: 31-32, fig. 4); FRETTER ET AL. (1986: 616-617, figs. 427-428); PEÑAS ET AL. (1996: 42, figs. 106-107); SOLUSTRI & MICALI (2004: 66, fig. 5f); SCUDERI & TERLIZZI (2012: pl.19, fig. 9); ÖZTÜRK ET AL. (2013a: 143-144, fig. 6); SCAPERROTTA ET AL. (2011: 113); HØISÆTER (2014: 32-34, figs 45-48).

Megastomia conoidea (Brocchi) – LANDAU ET AL. (2011: 40, pl. 22, fig. 6); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999a: 27-31, figs. 53-60, 91-92, 97); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2011: 381); GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL. (2014: figs. 119-122, appendix p. 61); OLIVER ET AL. (2015: 136, figs. 136-141); TRIGO ET AL. (2018: 361, fig. 20); LANDAU & MICALI (2021: 228-230, pl. 27, figs. 1-2).

Material examined (46 shells, 22 with soft parts, in 8 samples): Spain • 1 sh + 1 spc; 43°40.192'N, 08°43.760'W to 43°40.943'N, 08°42.366'W; 207-212 m; 8 sept. 2002; DA/02 ESB-200 • 8 sh + 2 spc; 43°26.703'N, 08°30.669'W to 43°27.452'N, 08°29.612'W; 102-103 m; 11 Sep. 2003; DA/03 EBS-100 • 10 spc; 43°31.970'N, 08°37.670 W to 43°32.697'N, 08°3.171'W; 151 m; 17 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-EBS-150 • 2 spc; 42°47.353'N, 09°25.161'W to 42°44.866'N, 09°25.913'W; 146-147 m; 18 Sep. 2004; VE/04

CA-EBS-150 • 2 spc; 42°29.455'N, 09°17.472'W to 42°31.292'N, 09°19.660'W; 147-149 m; 19 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-AT-150 • 15 sh + 4 spc; 43°29.412'N, 08°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 08°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 25 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-AT-110 • 1 sh; 43°58.84'N, 08°15.625'W to 43° 59.621'N, 08°14.285'W 233-237 m; 17 Jul. 2008; SE/08 ESB 20 • 3 sh; 43°29.139'N, 08°42.233'W to 43°29.596'N, 08°42.838'W; 149-151 m; 22 Jul. 2008; SE/08 DRN 22.

Type locality: Northern Italy (Pliocene).

This is a very common species with a very wide geographical distribution from Norway to Angola (including the islands of Madeira, Canaries, Cape Verde, São Tomé and Príncipe), the whole Mediterranean and Black Sea, from infralittoral to the deepest circalittoral bottoms (FRETTER *ET AL.*, 1986; WILKE & VAN AARTSEN, 1998; PEÑAS *ET AL.*, 2011; ÖZTÜRK *ET AL.*, 2013a; GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.*, 2014; HØISÆTER, 2014; BALLESTEROS *ET AL.*, 2019). It has

been found in some seamounts and banks of the Alboran Sea (PEÑAS *ET AL.*, 1996; CABALLERO-HERRERA *ET AL.*, 2023b). It has been recorded in Galicia by URGORRI & BESTEIRO (1983) and TRIGO *ET AL.* (2018). It was present in samples obtained between 102 and 237 m depth (alive in the range 102-212 m).

The wide geographical and bathymetric distribution of this taxon suggests that it may comprise a complex of cryptic species (PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 2011).

Genus *Brachystomia* Monterosato, 1884

Type species by subsequent designation: *Odostomia rissoides* Hanley, 1844.

Brachystomia eulimoides (Hanley, 1844) (Fig. 3A, B)

Odostomia eulimoides Hanley, 1844: 18.

Odostomia notata Jeffreys, 1848: 336.

Odostomia dubia Jeffreys, 1948: 338.

Odostomia eulimoides Hanley – RODRÍGUEZ BABÍO & THIRIOT-QUIÉVREUX (1974: 72, pl. 6 figs. K, O protoconch); VAN AARTSEN *ET AL.* (1984: 53, fig. 252); SCHANDER (1995: 59-60, fig. 1B); SMRIGLIO, CIOMMEI & MARIOTTINI (1995: 55-64, pl. 2, figs. 6-12, pl. 3, figs. 17-19); PEÑAS *ET AL.* (1996: 44, figs 132-133); WILKE & VAN AARTSEN (1998: 13-14, figs. 11, 26a-b); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999a: 96-98, figs. 255.259, 346-347); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2011: 386); SCAPERROTTA *ET AL.* (2011: 116); ÖZTÜRK *ET AL.* (2013a: 145-146, fig. 9); GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.* (2014: figs. 50-52, appendix p. 54); OLIVER *ET AL.* (2015: fig. 160).

Brachystomia eulimoides (Hanley) – FRETTER *ET AL.* (1986: 601-603, figs. 414-415); HØISÆTER (2014: 26-27, fig. 29); TRIGO *ET AL.* (2018: 361, fig. 23); LANDAU & MICALI (2021: 215-216, pl. 12, figs. 1-3); NOFRONI *ET AL.* (2022: 76-78, Fig. 1A-L).

Material examined (30 shells, 8 with soft parts, in 3 samples): Spain • 2 sh; 43°31.970'N, 08°37.670'W to 43°32.697'N, 08°3.171'W; 151 m; 17 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-EBS-150 • 14 sh; 43°29.412'N, 08°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 08°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 25 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-AT-110 • 6 sh + 8 spc; 43°26.703'N, 08°30.669'W to 43° 27.452'N, 08°29.612'W; 102-103 m; 11 Sep. 2003; DA/03 EBS-100.

Type locality: Guernsey, Channel Islands (HØISÆTER, 2014).

This is a common species with a very wide distribution from Iceland, Norway and Faroe Islands to Angola, the Mediterranean and the Black Sea (FRETTER *ET AL.*, 1986; WILKE & VAN AARTSEN, 1998; PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 1999a; ÖZTÜRK *ET AL.*, 2013a; HØISÆTER, 2014;

BALLESTEROS *ET AL.*, 2019), mainly in infralittoral bottoms. It has been recorded in Galicia by URGORRI & BESTEIRO (1983) and TRIGO *ET AL.* (2018). Eight of the shells were found with soft parts in the shallowest sample studied.

Figure 3. A, B: *Brachystomia eulimoides* (Hanley, 1844), shell from VE/04 GA-AT-110 (2.8 × 1.2 mm) and protoconch; C, D: *Brachystomia cf. scalaris* (MacGillivray, 1843), shell from VE/04 GA-AT-110 (1.8 × 0.9 mm) and protoconch.

Figura 3. A, B: *Brachystomia eulimoides* (Hanley, 1844), concha de VE/04 GA-AT-110 (2,8 × 1,2 mm) y protoconcha; C, D: *Brachystomia cf. scalaris* (MacGillivray, 1843), concha de VE/04 GA-AT-110 (1,8 × 0,9 mm) y protoconcha.

Brachystomia cf. scalaris (MacGillivray, 1843) (Fig. 3C, D)

Odostomia scalaris MacGillivray, 1843: 154.

Odostomia rissoides Hanley, 1844: 18 – HARMER (1923: 834, pl. 64, figs 13, 14).

Brachystomia rissoides (Hanley) – FRETTER ET AL. (1986: 599-601, figs 412, 413).

Odostomia scalaris MacGillivray – RODRÍGUEZ BABÍO & THIRIOT-QUIÉVREUX (1975: 500, pl. 1, figs. L- M); VAN AARTSEN (1987: 12, fig. 22); PEÑAS ET AL. (1996: 52, figs. 136, 137); WILKE & VAN AARTSEN (1998: 14, figs. 12, 27a-b); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999a: 76,-78 figs. 191-207, 341-342); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2011: 383); SCAPERROTTA ET AL. (2011: 121); GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL. (2014: figs 67-68, appendix p. 56); TRIGO ET AL. (2018: 362, fig. 27).

Brachystomia scalaris (MacGillivray) – HØISÆTER (2014: 27, figs. 30-33); LANDAU & MICALI (2021: 216-217, pl. 13, figs. 1-2).

Material examined (11 shells, 1 with soft parts, in 2 samples): Spain • 1 spc; 43°40.192'N, 08°43.760'W to 43°40.943'N, 08°42.366'W; 207-212 m; 8 Sept. 2002; DA/02 ESB-200 • 16 sh; 43°29.412'N, 08°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 08°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 25 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-AT-110.

Type locality: near Aberdeen, Scotland.

This species is widely distributed in the eastern Atlantic from Norway to Angola, and in the Mediterranean and Black Sea (WILKE & VAN AARTSEN, 1998; PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 1999a; HØISÆTER, 2014; BALLESTEROS ET AL., 2019), but the interpretation of this taxon by different authors is somewhat confusing and may comprise a complex of cryptic species. We have considered here as

Brachystomia cf. scalaris those shells similar to *O. eulimoides* but proportionally somewhat wider, with a protoconch of type C instead type B (Fig. 3). Some empty shells were found in a sample at 110-111 m, and one living specimens was found in another sample at 207-212 m. It has been recorded in Galicia by URGORRI & BESTEIRO (1983) and TRIGO ET AL. (2018).

Figure 4. *Odostomia acuta* Jeffreys, 1848 from VE/04 AG EBS-150. A-B: shell (1.4 × 0.7mm) and protoconch; C-E: shell (1.1 × 0.6 mm), protoconch and detail of its microsculpture; F: apical view of the protoconch.

Figura 4. *Odostomia acuta* Jeffreys, 1848 de VE/04 AG EBS-150. A-B: concha (1,4 × 0,7 mm) y protoconcha; C-E: concha (1,1 × 0,6 mm), protoconcha y detalle de su microscultura; F: vista apical de la protoconcha.

Genus *Odostomia* Fleming, 1813

Type species by subsequent designation: *Turbo plicatus* Montagu, 1803.

Odostomia acuta Jeffreys, 1848 (Fig. 4)

Odostomia acuta Jeffreys, 1848: 338-339 – RODRÍGUEZ BABÍO & THIRIOT-QUIÉVREUX (1975: 498-499, pl. 1, figs. A-C protoconch); VAN AARTSEN *ET AL.* (1984: 51, fig. 248); MICALI (1983b: 33, 35, fig. 1); FRETTER *ET AL.* (1986: 612-613, figs. 423-424); NOFRONI (1988: 10, fig 2); PEÑAS *ET AL.* (1996: 39-40, figs. 108-109); WILKE & VAN AARTSEN (1998: 11, pl. 8, fig. 23); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999a: 58-60, figs. 131-136); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2011: 381); ÖZTÜRK *ET AL.* (2013a: 141, fig. 2A-B); GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.* (2014: fig. 44, appendix p. 54); HØISÆTER (2014: 31-32, figs. 38-42 including living animal); OLIVER *ET AL.* (2015: figs. 146-148); NEKHAEV (2017: 61-62, fig. 2D-F); TRIGO *ET AL.* (2018: fig. 17); LANDAU & MICALI (2021: 232-233, pl. 31, figs. 1-2).

Material examined (more than 350 shells, most of them with soft parts, in 9 samples): Spain • 10 sh + 2 spc; 43°35.451'N, 08°34.432'W to 43°34.810'N, 08°35.407'W; 153-151 m; 8 Sep. 2002; DAI/02 EBS-150 • 3 spc; 43°40.192'N, 08°43.760'W to 43°40.943'N, 08°42.366'W; 207-212 m; 8 Sep. 2002; DAI/02 EBS-200 • 10 sh; 43°26.703'N, 08°30.669'W to 43°27.452'N, 08°29.612'W; 102-103 m; 11 Sep. 2003; DA/03 EBS-100 • 3 spc; 43°35.451'N, 08°34.432'W to 43°34.810'N, 08°35.407'W; 153-151 m; 14 Sep. 2003; DA/03 EBS-150 • > 300 spc; 42°47.353'N, 09°25.161'W to 42°44.866'N, 09°25.913'W; 146-147 m; 18 Sep. 2004; VE/04 CA-EBS-150 • 20 spc; 42°31.176'N, 09°23.380'W to 42°32.132'N, 09°24.151'W; 242-248 m; 19 Sep. 2004; VE/04 AG-EBS-250 • 1 spc; 43°35.611'N, 08°58.536'W to 43°36.104'N, 08°57.284'W; 384-345 m; 24 Sep. 2004; VE/04 AG-EBS-400 • 3 sh; 43°29.412'N, 08°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 08°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 25 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-AT-110 • 1 sh; 43°58.84'N, 08°15.625'W to 43° 59.621'N, 08°14.285' W 233-237 m; 17 Jul. 2008; SE/08 ESB 20.

Type locality: Not designated (WARÉN 1980).

This is a very common species widely distributed from the southwestern Barents Sea (HØISÆTER, 2014; NEKHAEV, 2017) south to Angola (recorded in the British Isles, northwestern Spain, Morocco, Mauritania, Senegal, Guinea Conakry, Ghana, Angola, Madeira, Selvagens, Canary and Cape Verde islands, and the whole Mediterranean and Black Sea, mainly in

circalittoral bottoms (FRETTER *ET AL.*, 1986; WILKE & VAN AARTSEN, 1998; PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 1999a; 201; ÖZTÜRK *ET AL.*, 2013a; TRIGO *ET AL.*, 2018; CABALLERO-HERRERA *ET AL.*, 2023b). It has turned out to be the most abundant species in the studied samples, collected in the depth range 102-384 m. More than 300 living specimens were found in a sample at 146-147 m.

Ostostomia unidentata (Montagu, 1803) (Fig. 5)

Turbo unidentatus Montagu, 1803: 324.

Turbonilla albella Loven, 1846: 49, pl.1 fig. 11.

Ostostomia unidentata (Montagu): – RODRÍGUEZ BABIO & THIRIOT-QUIÉVREUX (1975: 499, pl. 1, figs. D-F); MICALI (1983b: 35, fig. 2); FRETTER *ET AL.* (1986: 614-615, figs. 425-426); VAN AARTSEN (1987: 11-12, figs 17, 3,-37); SCHANDER (1995: 57-58, fig. 1A); PEÑAS *ET AL.* (1996: 154, figs. 114-115); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999a: 63-65, figs. 153-161); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2011: 382); SCAPERROTTA *ET AL.* (2011: 124); ÖZTÜRK *ET AL.* (2013a: 150-151, fig. 21); HØISÆTER (2014: 38, 41, figs. 63-67); GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.* (2014: figs. 76-77, appendix p. 57); PEÑAS *ET AL.* (2014: 150-152, figs. 16A-B); OLIVER *ET AL.* (2015: figs. 142-143); LANDAU & MICALI (2021: 242-244, plate 46, figs 1-3); NOFRONI *ET AL.* (2022: 78-79, Fig. 2A-P).

Material examined (7 shells, 2 with soft parts, in 3 samples): Spain • 2 spc; 43°33.960'N; 08°36.709'W to 43°34.329'N 08°36.411'W; 151-155 m; 8 Sep. 2002; DAI/02 AT-150 • 3 sh; 43°29.412'N, 08°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 08°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 25 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-AT-110 • 2 sh; 43°58.84'N, 08°15.625'W to 43° 59.621'N, 08°14.285' W 233-237 m; 17 Jul. 2008; SE/08 ESB 20.

Type locality: Salcombe Bay, Devon, southwestern England, deep-water.

This species is widely distributed in the eastern Atlantic from the Faroe Islands and Norway to Angola, including Madeira, Canary and Cape Verde Islands, and the Mediterranean, mainly in circalittoral bottoms (FRETTER *ET AL.*, 1986; SCHANDER, 1995; PEÑAS & ROLÁN 1999a; ÖZTÜRK *ET AL.*, 2013; HØISÆTER, 2014; PEÑAS *ET AL.*, 2014).

NOFRONI *ET AL.* (2022) discussed this taxon extensively and recorded specimens in the upper bathyal down to 550 m depth. We found few shells, two of them with soft parts in a sample collected at 151-155 m. URGORRI & BESTEIRO (1983) and PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999a) recorded *O. unidentata* in Galicia.

Figure 5. *Odostomia unidentata* (Montagu, 1803) from DAI/02 AT-150. A, B: shell (1.4 × 0.8 mm) and protoconch; C: broken shell (2.5 × 1.1mm) showing its columella (SE/08 EBS-20); D: basal view; E: apical view of the protoconch.

Figura 5. Odostomia unidentata (Montagu, 1803) de DAI/02 AT-150. A, B: concha (1,4 × 0,8 mm) y protoconcha; C: concha rota (2,5 × 1,1 mm) mostrando su columela (SE/08 EBS-20); D: vista basal; E: vista apical de la protoconcha.

Odostomia suboblonga Jeffreys, 1884 (Fig. 6)

Odostomia suboblonga Jeffreys, 1884: 345-346; pl. 26 fig. 3.

Odostomia suboblonga Jeffreys – VAN AARTSEN (1987: 12, fig. 21); PEÑAS *ET AL.* (1996: 52-53, fig. 122); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2011: 384); GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.* (2014: figs. 70-71, appendix p. 56); PEÑAS *ET AL.* (2014: 150, fig. 15H-K).

Material examined (10 shells, 4 with soft parts, in 8 samples): Spain • 1 sh; 43°40.192'N, 08°43.760'W to 43°40.943'N, 08°42.366'W; 207-212 m; 8 Sep. 2002; DAI/02 EBS-200 • 2 sh + 1 spc; 43°51.873'N, 08°53.683'W to 43°53.120'N, 08°53.301'W; 802-788 m; 15 Sep. 2003; DAI/83 EBS-800 • 2 sh; 43°53.847'N, 08°57.324'W to 43°54.621'N, 08°57.261'W; 993-1004 m; 16 Sep. 2003; DAI/03 AT-1000 • 1 spc; 43°48.587'N, 08°51.402'W to 43°49.545'N, 08°51.197'W; 610-598 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DAI/03 EBS-600 • 1 spc; 43°35.611'N, 08°58.536'W to 43°36.104'N, 08°57.284'W; 384-345 m; 24 Sep. 2004; VE/04 AG-EBS-400 • 2 sh + 1 spc; 43°58.84'N, 08°15.625'W to 43°59.621'N, 08°14.285'W; 233-237 m; 16 Jul. 2008; SE/08 EBS-20 • 1 spc; 44°06.943'N, 08°47.232'W to 44°07.173'N, 08°46.031'W; 440-429 m; 17 Jul. 2008; SE/08 EBS-11-2 • 1 sh; 44°07.628'N, 08°45.871'W to 44°07.989'N, 08°45.542'W; 412-411 m; 19 Jul. 2008; SE/08 DRN-11-4.

Type locality: Not designated. Syntypes from several stations of the Porcupine expedition (WARÉN, 1980; VAN AARTSEN, 1987).

Figure 6. *Odostomia suboblonga* Jeffreys, 1884 from DAI/03 EBS-800. A: shell (1.9 × 1.1 mm); B: shell (1.5 × 1.0 mm); C: protoconch; D: detail of the peripheral sulcus of another shell.

Figura 6. *Odostomia suboblonga* Jeffreys, 1884 de DAI/03 EBS-800. A: concha (1,9 × 1,1 mm); B: concha (1,5 × 1,0 mm); C: protoconcha; D: detalle del surco periférico de otra concha.

This species is known from the Porcupine Bank (west of Ireland), Bay of Biscay, Ibero-Moroccan Gulf, Madeira, Selvagens and Canary Islands, and in the western Mediterranean, in circalittoral and bathyal bottoms (PEÑAS *ET AL.*, 1996, 2014; PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 2011;

GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.*, 2014; UTRILLA *ET AL.*, 2020). Several shells were found in samples collected between 200 and 1000 m (living specimens between 233 and 802 m) which seems to be the first record for northern Spain.

Genus *Doliella* Monterosato, 1880

Type species by monotypy: *Odostomia nitens* Jeffreys, 1870.

Doliella nitens (Jeffreys, 1870) (Fig. 7)

Odostomia nitens Jeffreys, 1870: 79.

Odostomia nitens Jeffreys – PEÑAS *ET AL.* (1996: figs. 94-95); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999a: 116, fig. 355); SCAPERROTTA *ET AL.* (2013: 99).

Liostomia nitens Jeffreys – PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2011: 388).

Doliella nitens (Jeffreys) – GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.* (2014: fig. 129, appendix p. 62); LANDAU & MICALI (2021: 217-218, plate 14, figs. 1-2).

Material examined (11 shells, 2 with soft parts, in 7 samples): Spain • 1 spc; 43°51.873'N, 08°53.683'W to 43°53.120'N, 08°53.301'W; 802-788 m; 15 Sep. 2003; DAI/83 EBS-800 • 1 sh; 43°53.847'N, 08°57.324'W to 43°54.621'N, 08°57.261'W; 993-1004 m; 16 Sep. 2003; DAI/03 AT-

Figure 7. *Doliella nitens* (Jeffreys, 1870). A-C: shell (4.2 × 1.5 mm) from SE/08 DRN 15-2B, aperture and suture; D: protoconch from SE/08 DRN 7-1.

Figura 7. Doliella nitens (Jeffreys, 1870). A-C: concha (4,2 × 1,5 mm) de SE/08 DRN 15-2B, abertura y sutura; D: protoconcha de SE/08 DRN 7-1.

1000 • 2 sh; 43°48.587'N, 08°51.402'W to 43°49.545'N, 08°51.197'W; 610-598 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DAI/03 EBS-600 • 2 sh; 43°36.544'N, 09°03.064'W to 43°36.816'N, 09°04.339'W; 601-619 m; 28 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-EBS-600 • 1 spc; 44°08.461'N, 09°04.634'W to 44°08.607'N, 09°04.413'W; 917-896 m; 20 Jul. 2008; SE/06 DRN-7-1 • 1 sh; 44°06.84'N, 09°03.692'W to 44°07.075'N, 09°03.655'W; 911-886 m; 20 Jul. 2008; SE/06 DRN-7-2 • 3 sh; 43°55.886'N, 08°54.846'W to 43°55.291'N, 08°55.65'W; 933-930 m; 24 Jul. 2008; SE/06 DRN-15-2b.

Type locality: Hydra channel (130 fathoms), Greece (WARÉN, 1980).

This species is known in the Ibero-Moroccan Gulf, Azores, Canary and Cape Verde Islands, and in the western Mediterranean, in circalittoral and bathyal bottoms (PEÑAS *ET AL.*, 1996, 2014; VAN AARTSEN *ET AL.*, 1998; PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 2011; SCAPERROTTA *ET AL.*,

2013; GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.*, 2014). Some shells found in samples collected between 610 and 1004 m (specimens with soft parts in the range 802-917 m) are the first record from northern Spain, expanding northwards its known distribution.

Genus *Liostomia* Sars, 1878

Type species by subsequent designation: *Turbonilla clavula* Lovén, 1846.

Liostomia clavula (Lovén, 1846) (Fig. 8)

Turbonilla clavula Lovén, 1846: 49, pl. 1, fig. 7.

Eulimella clavula Lovén – Forbes & Hanley (1850-51: 314-316, fig. 8).

Odostomia clavulus Lovén – PEÑAS *ET AL.* (1996: 42, fig. 96); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999a: 116, figs. 309-310).

Liostomia clavulus – PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2011: 388).

Figure 8. *Liostomia clavula* (Lovén, 1846) from VE/04 GA EBS-150. A: shell (1.5 × 0.7 mm); B: suture; C: umbilical area; D: protoconch.

Figura 8. *Liostomia clavula* (Lovén, 1846) de VE/04 GA EBS-150. A: concha (1,5 × 0,7 mm); B: sutura; C: zona umbilical; D: protoconcha.

Liostomia clavula – FRETTER ET AL. (1986: 587-590, figs. 402-404); WARÉN (1991: 106-107, fig. 35 C-D, G); ÖZTÜRK ET AL. (2013a: 151-152, fig. 23); GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL. (2014: fig. 112, appendix p. 61); HØISÆTER (2014: 51, figs. 85-89); LANDAU & MICALI (2021: 219-218, plate 16, figs. 1-2).

Material examined (37 shells, 26 with soft parts, in 6 samples): Spain • 1 spc; 43°35.451'N, 08°34.432'W to 43°34.810'N, 08°35.407'W; 153-151 m; 14 Sep. 2002; DAI/02 EBS-150 • 1 sh + 1 spc; 43°34.127'N, 08°36.562'W to 43°34.820'N, 08°35.585'W; 152-149 m; 14 Sep. 2003; DAI/03 EBS-150 • 1 sh + 4 spc; 42°47,353'N, 09°25,161'W to 42°44,866'N, 09°25,913'W; 146-147 m; 18 Sep. 2004; VE/04 CA-EBS-150 • 11 spc + 1 sh; 42°50.507'N, 09°25.773'W to 42°48.810'N, 09°25.198'W; 151-148 m; 18 Sep. 2004; VE/04 CA-EBS-150 • 2 sp + 1 spc; 42°29,455'N, 09°17,472'W to 42°31,292'N, 09°19.660'W; 147-149 m; 19 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-AT-150 • 3 sh; 43°29.412'N, 08°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 08°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 25 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-AT-110.

Type locality: Gullmarsfjord, Swedish west coast (WARÉN, 1991).

This species is known from western Norway and Skagerrak to Angola, including Canary and Cape Verde Islands, and the Mediterranean, mainly in the depth range 20-100 m (FRETTER ET AL., 1986; WARÉN, 1991; ÖZTÜRK ET AL.,

2013; HØISÆTER, 2014). It was recorded in Galicia by PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999a) and TRIGO ET AL. (2018). Several living specimens were found in five samples collected in the narrow depth range 146-153 m.

Liostomia afzelii Warén, 1991 (Fig. 9)

Liostomia afzelii Warén, 1991: 106-108, figs. 35A-B, 36A.

Odostomia afzelii (Warén) – PEÑAS ET AL. (1996: 40, fig. 97); GIRIBET & PEÑAS (1997: 76: fig. 75).

Figure 9. *Liostomia afzelii* Warén, 1991, from DAI/03 EBS-100. A: shell (1.8 × 0.6 mm); B-D: juvenile shell, detail of its growth lines and umbilicus; E: suture at insertion of the aperture; F: protoconch. *Figura 9. Liostomia afzelii* Warén, 1991, de DAI/03 EBS-100. A: *concha* (1,8 × 0,6 mm); B-D: *concha* juvenil, detalle de sus líneas de crecimiento y ombligo; E: *sutura* en la inserción de la apertura; F: *protoconcha*.

Liostomia afzelii Warén – SOLUSTRI & MICALI (2004: 65, fig. 4a); ÖZTÜRK *ET AL.* (2013a: 151, fig. 22); GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.* (2014: fig. 111, appendix p. 60); HØISÆTER (2014: 51, figs. 84, 89); LANDAU & MICALI (2021: 218-219, plate 15, fig. 1).

Material examined (28 shells, 15 with soft parts, in 5 samples): Spain • 1 sh; 43°35.451'N, 08°34.432'W to 43°34.810'N, 08°35.407'W; 153-151 m; 14 Sep. 2002; DAI/02 EBS-150 • 4 sh + 8 spc; 43°26.703'N, 08°30,669'W to 43° 27.452'N, 08° 29,612'W; 102-103 m; 11 Sep. 2003; DAI/03 EBS-100 • 9 sh; 43°34.127'N, 08°36.562'W to 43°34.820'N, 08°35.585'W; 152-149 m; 14 Sep. 2003; DAI/03 EBS-150 • 2 sh + 4 spc; 43°31.970'N, 08°37.670 W to 43°32.697'N, 08°3.171'W; 151 m; 17 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-EBS-150 • 3 sh; 43°29.412'N, 08°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 08°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 25 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-AT-110.

Type locality: South Lilleskär, Koster area, Swedish west coast, 30-40 m (HØISÆTER, 2014).

This species is known from western Norway to the Mediterranean in the depth range 20-200 m (WARÉN, 1991; SOLUSTRI & MICALI, 2004; ÖZTÜRK *ET AL.*, 2013; GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.*, 2014; HØISÆTER, 2014). Several living

specimens were found in two samples collected between 102 and 151 m and are the first record for northern Spain. They differ from *L. clavula* mainly in being broader and having nearly one whorl less at the same size. VAN

Letras y pie
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Figure 10. *Liostomia hansgei* Warén, 1991, from VE/04 AG EBS-150. A: shell (2 × 1 mm); B, C: protoconch; D, E: details.

Figura 10. *Liostomia hansgei* Warén, 1991, de VE/04 AG EBS-150. A: concha (2 × 1 mm); B, C: protoconcha; D, E: detalles.

AARTSEN (pers. comm. in HØISÆTER, 2014) expressed the view that they could be extreme variants of the same

species but molecular data in SCHANDER ET AL. (2003) support keeping them separate.

Liostomia hansgei Warén, 1991 (Fig. 10)

Liostomia hansgei Warén, 1991: 108, figs. 35E-F, 36C.

Odostomia hansgei (Warén) – PEÑAS ET AL. (1996: 46 figs. 98-99); GIRIBET & PEÑAS (1997: 76: fig. 76).

Liostomia hansgei Warén – GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL. (2014: figs. 114-116, appendix p. 61); HØISÆTER (2014: 53, figs. 87-89).

Material examined (2 shells, 1 with soft parts, in 1 sample): Spain • 1 sh + 1 spc; 43°31.970'N, 08°37.670' W to 43°32.697'N, 08°37.171'W; 151 m; 17 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-EBS-150.

Type locality: South Lilleskär, Koster area, Swedish west coast, 30-40 m (HØISÆTER, 2014).

This is a rare species only known from few records in Scandinavia and the Western Mediterranean in infralittoral and circalittoral bottoms (WARÉN, 1991; PEÑAS ET AL., 1996; GIRIBET & PEÑAS,

1997; GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL., 2014; HØISÆTER, 2014). Two shells, one of them with soft parts, were found in the same sample at 151 m depth and are the first record for northern Spain.

Figure 11. *Ondina divisa* (Adams, 1797) from SE/08 EBS-14. A: shell (1.6 × 0.7 mm); B: detail of its microsculpture; C: protoconch.

Figura 11. *Ondina divisa* (Adams, 1797) de SE/08 EBS-14. A: concha (1,6 × 0,7 mm); B: detalle de su microescultura; C: protoconcha.

Genus *Ondina* de Folin, 1870

Type species by subsequent monotypy: *Ondina semiornata* de Folin 1872, accepted as *Ondina warreni* (Thompson, 1845).

Ondina divisa (Adams, 1797) (Fig. 11)

Turbo divisus Adams, 1797: 254.

Turbo insculptus Montagu, 1808: 129-130.

Odostomia insculpta Montagu – JEFFREYS (1867: 139-140).

Menestho divisa (Adams) – URCORRI & BESTEIRO (1983: 10).

Evalea divisa (Adams) – FRETTER *ET AL.* (1986: 581-582, figs. 394-396).

Ondina divisa (Adams) – VAN AARTSEN (1987: 19, fig. 48); WARÉN (1991: 103, figs. 30C, 36E-F, 39D); SCHANDER (1995: 60); PEÑAS *ET AL.* (1996: fig. 147); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2011: 389); HØISÆTER (2014: 44, figs. 70-74).

Material examined (6 shells, 1 with soft parts, in 4 samples): Spain • 1 spc; 43°35.451'N, 08°34.432'W to 43°34.810'N, 08°35.407'W; 153-151 m; 14 Sep. 2002; DAI/02 EBS-150 • 1 sh; 43°26.703'N, 08°30.669'W to 43°27.452'N, 08°29.612'W; 102-103 m; 11 Sep. 2003; DAI/03 EBS-100) 1 spc; 43°31.970'N, 08°37.670'W to 43° 32. 697'N, 08°3.171'W; 151 m; 17 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-EBS-150 • 3 sh; 43°29.412'N, 08°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 08°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 25 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-AT-110 • 1 sh; 44°00.806'N, 08°33.098'W to 44°01.967'N, 08°32.57'W; 346-344 m; 17 Jul. 2008; SE/08 EBS-14.

Type locality: Ilfracombe, Devon, southwestern England (WARÉN, 1991).

This species is known in the Atlantic from Iceland, Faroe Islands and Norway south to the Bay of Biscay, Galicia and Madeira in circalittoral bottoms (FRETTER *ET AL.*, 1986; WARÉN, 1991; SCHANDER, 1995; PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 2011;

HØISÆTER, 2014). In the Mediterranean it has only been recorded in the Alboran Sea (PEÑAS *ET AL.*, 2006). Some shells were found in samples collected in the depth range 110-346 m, one of them with soft parts at 151-153 m.

Genus *Pyrgulina* Adams, 1863

Type species by subsequent designation: *Chrysallida casta* Adams, 1861.

Pyrgulina stefanisi (Jeffreys, 1869) (Fig. 12)

Rissoa costulata S.V. Wood, 1848: 106, pl. 11, fig. 12 a-b

Rissoa stefanisi Jeffreys, 1869: 208, pl. 6, fig. 31.

Chrysallida pygmaea (Grateloup, 1838: 282, pl. 6, figs. 77-78) – VAN AARTSEN (1977: 54, pl. 2, fig. 11); MICALI ET AL. (1993: 151-153).

Chrysallida stefanisi (Jeffreys) – WARÉN (1991: fig. 32D, p. 101); VAN DER LINDEN & EIKENBOOM (1992: 42-44, figs 51-52); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1998: 28-30); ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (1999: 78).

Chrysallida (Pyrgulina) stefanisi (Jeffreys) – VAN AARTSEN ET AL. (2000: 38).

Kongsrudia stefanisi (Jeffreys) – GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL. (2014: fig. 152, appendix p. 65).

Pyrgulina stefanisi (Jeffreys) – PEÑAS ET AL. (2014: fig. 5H); CEULEMANS, VAN DINGENEN & LANDAU (2018: 132-133, pl. 8, fig. 6); LANDAU & MICALI (2021: 275-276, pl. 81, figs. 1-2).

Material examined (2 empty shells in 1 sample): Spain • 2 sh; 43°57.030'N, 08°54.795'W to 43°57.248'N, 08°54.133'W; 1191-1132 m; 9 Sep. 2002; DAI/02 AT-1000.

Type locality: Sicily (LANDAU & MICALI, 2021).

This species is known from deep water of the central and western Mediterranean, Ibero-Moroccan Gulf, Mauritania, Azores, Madeira and Canary islands, from circalittoral to bathyal bottoms (VAN DER LINDEN & EIKENBOOM, 1992; MICALI ET AL., 1993; VAN AARTSEN ET AL., 2000; GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL.,

2014; PEÑAS ET AL., 2014; UTRILLA ET AL., 2020). MICALI ET AL. (1993) discussed the synonymy of this taxon and concluded that the fossil and Recent forms are conspecific. We have found two empty shells (one of them broken) in the same sample collected at 1132-1191 m. This is the first record for northern Spain.

Genus *Spiralina* Chaster, 1898 (= *Spiralinella* Chaster, 1901)

Type species by monotypy: *Turbo spiralis* Montagu, 1803.

Spiralina spiralis (Montagu, 1803) (Fig. 39J)

Turbo spiralis Montagu, 1803: 323.

Chrysallida pellucida (Dillwyn, 1817: 528) – SCHANDER (1995: 56-57); NOFRONI & SCHANDER (1984: 8, fig. 1c); PEÑAS ET AL. (1996: 28, fig. 12); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2011: 369).

Partulida spiralis (Montagu) – FRETTER ET AL. (1986: 573-575, fig. 390-391).

Partulida pellucida (Dillwyn) – GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL. (2014: figs. 213-214, appendix p. 71).

Chrysallida spiralis (Montagu) – RODRÍGUEZ BABÍO & THIRIOT-QUIÉVREUX (1975: 503, pl. 3, figs. J-L protoconch); WARÉN (1991: 95, fig. 29C); VAN DER LINDEN & EIKENBOOM (1992: 9-11, figs. 18-19).

Spiralinella spiralis (Montagu) – HØISÆTER (2014: 19-21, figs. 16-20).

Material examined (9 shells, 7 with soft parts, in 2 samples): Spain • 2 sh; 42°29.455'N, 09°17.472'W to 42°31.292'N, 09°19.660'W; 147-149 m; 19 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-AT-150 • 7 spc; 43°29.412'N, 08°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 08°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 25 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-AT-110.

Type locality: Salcombe Bay, Devon, southwestern England (WARÉN, 1991).

This species is known from Iceland and northern Norway to Portugal and the western Mediterranean, mainly in

infralittoral bottoms (FRETTER ET AL., 1986; WARÉN, 1991; VAN DEN LINDEN & EIKENBOOM, 1992; PEÑAS & ROLÁN,

Figure 12. *Pyrgulina stefanisi* (Jeffreys, 1869) from DA/II AT-1000. A, B: shell (1.6 × 1.0 mm) and protoconch; C-E: broken shell (1.0 mm), protoconch and detail of microsculpture of the teleoconch. *Figura 12. Pyrgulina stefanisi* (Jeffreys, 1869) de DA/II AT-1000. A, B: concha (1,6 × 1,0 mm) y protoconcha; C-E: concha rota (1,0 mm), protoconcha y detalle de microescultura de la teleoconcha.

2011; HØISÆTER, 2014). It has been recorded in Galicia by URGORRI & BESTEIRO (1983) and TRIGO *ET AL.* (2018).

Seven living specimens were found in a sample collected at 110-111 m, and two empty shells at 147-149 m.

Genus *Parthenina* Bucquoy, Dautzenberg & Dollfus, 1883

Type species by original designation: *Turbo interstinctus* Adams, 1797.

Parthenina cf. interstincta (J. Adams, 1797) (Fig. 39E-G)

Turbo interstinctus J. Adams, 1797: 66, pl. 13, figs 23, 24.

Jamina obtusa Brown, 1827: 50, figs 27, 28.

Figure 13. *Parthenina multicostata* (Jeffreys, 1884) from VE/04 GA-AT-110. A: shell (1.2 × 0.8 mm); B: protoconch.

Figura 13. *Parthenina multicostata* (Jeffreys, 1884) de VE/04 GA-AT-110. A: concha (1,2 × 0,8 mm); B: protoconcha.

Chrysallida obtusa (Brown) – RODRÍGUEZ BABÍO & THIRIOT-QUIÉVREUX (1975: 503, pl. 3, figs. G-I protoconch); VAN AARTSEN (1977: 57, pl. 3, fig. 22); FRETTER ET AL. (1986: 561-562, fig. 378); VAN DER LINDEN & EIKENBOOM (1992: 23, figs. 8-9, 30-32); WILKE & VAN AARTSEN (1998: 10, pl. 4, fig. 19a-c); VAN AARTSEN ET AL. (2000: 28, fig. 33); ÖZTÜRK ET AL. (2011: 71, fig. 17); SCAPER-ROTTA ET AL. (2011: 104).

Chrysallida interstincta (Adams) – WARÉN (1991: 95, fig. 29A-B, G); PEÑAS ET AL. (1996: 22-24, figs. 43-44, 51); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1998: 42-44, figs. 118-126); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2011: 372); SCUDERI & TERLIZZI (2012: pl. 20, figs. 10-11).

Parthenina interstincta (Adams) – PEÑAS ET AL. (2014: 112, fig. 2E); HØISÆTER (2014: 16, figs. 6-11); GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL. (2014: figs. 158-162, appendix p. 67); LANDAU & MICALI (2021: 265-266, pl. 69, figs. 1-2).

Material examined (10 shells, 1 with soft parts, in 5 samples): Spain • 3 sh; 43°26.703'N, 08°30.669'W to 43°27.452'N, 08°29.612'W; 102-103 m; 11 Sep. 2003; DAI/03 EBS-100 • 1 spc; 43°31.970'N, 08°37.670'W to 43° 32.697'N, 08°37.171'W; 151 m; 17 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-EBS-150 • 5 sh; 43°29.412'N, 08°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 08°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 25 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-AT-110 • 1 sh; 43°58.84'N, 08°15.625'W to 43°59.621'N, 08°14.285'W 233-237 m; 17 Jul. 2008; SE/08 ESB 20.

Type locality: Bigbury Bay, Devonshire, England. Neotype selected by WARÉN (1991: fig. 39C, p. 113).

There has been considerable confusion about this taxon, which needs a thorough review. It has been diversely interpreted by different authors, who described some varieties, and it may include a complex of cryptic species (see JEFFREYS, 1884; BUCQUOY, DAUTZENBERG & DOLLFUS, 1882-1886; VAN AARTSEN, 1977; VAN DER LINDEN & EIKENBOOM, 1992; HØISÆTER, 2014). It has been widely recorded from southwestern Iceland and

northern Norway (WARÉN, 1991; HØISÆTER, 2014) to Angola, including Madeira, Canary and Cape Verde islands, the whole Mediterranean and Black Sea, in infralittoral and circalittoral bottoms (PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 2011, 2014). Some shells were found in the studied samples in the depth range 102-237 m, one of them with soft parts at 151 m. Until this taxon is clarified, we prefer to refer the studied shells as *P. cf. interstincta*.

Figure 14. *Parthenina flexuosa* (Monterosato, 1874) from DAI/03 EBS-800. A: shell (1.7 × 0.8 mm); B: protoconch; C: detail of the umbilical area.

Figura 14. *Parthenina flexuosa* (Monterosato, 1874) de DAI/03 EBS-800. A: concha (1,7 × 0,8 mm); B: protoconcha; C: detalle de la zona umbilical.

Parthenina multicosata (Jeffreys, 1884) (Fig. 13)

Odostomia interstincta var. *multicosata* Jeffreys, 1884: 353.

Chrysallida (*Parthenina*) *multicosata* (Jeffreys) – VAN AARTSEN *ET AL.* (2000: 29-30, fig. 34).

Chrysallida multicosata (Jeffreys) – MICALI & NOFRONI (2004: 179, fig. 7); PEÑAS *ET AL.* (2006: p. 130-131, fig. 308); OLIVER (2007: 56, fig. 72); PEÑAS *ET AL.* (2009: figs. 25-26); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2011: 372).

Parthenina multicosata (Jeffreys) – PEÑAS *ET AL.* (2014: 114, fig. 2G); GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.* (2014: fig. 173, appendix p. 67).

Material examined (4 shells, 1 with soft parts, in 2 samples): Spain • 1 sh; 43°26.703'N, 08°30.669'W to 43°27.452'N, 08°29.612'W; 102-103 m; 11 Sep. 2003; DAI/03 EBS-100; • 1 spc + 2 sh; 43°29.412'N, 08°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 08°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 25 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-AT-110.

Type locality: originally Porcupine 1870 expedition stn Cape Sagres (SE Portugal). VAN AARTSEN *ET AL.* (2000) designated as neotype a shell from the Ria de Arosa (which becomes the current type locality), dredged between 3 and 85 m.

This species has been recorded from Galicia to Ghana, common in Mauritania (VAN AARTSEN *ET AL.*, 2000), and in the western Mediterranean, mainly in the Alboran Sea in circalittoral bottoms (PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 2014). *Chrysallida multicosata* differs from *C. interstincta* by its larger size and higher number of ribs, which are flexuous somewhat opisthocline. Four shells, one of them with soft

parts, were found in the shallowest samples. The material cited by JEFFREYS (1884) from off Cape St Vincent comes from the outer shelf at 45-58 fathoms (82-106 m), in agreement with our datum (102-111 m); the depth of the type locality from the neotype (VAN AARTSEN *ET AL.*, 2000) is undeterminate between 3 and 85 m, probably closer to the latter, in Ria de Arousa, Galicia.

Parthenina flexuosa (Monterosato, 1874) (Fig. 14)

Odostomia flexuosa Monterosato, 1874: 267.

Chrysallida flexuosa (Monterosato) – VAN AARTSEN (1977: pl. 4, fig. 25); WARÉN (1991: fig. 32E-F); MICALI *ET AL.* (1993: 147-148, fig. 1); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999: 154, figs. 4-8); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2011: 369); SCAPERROTTA, BARTOLINI & BOGI (2012: 114); NEGRI & CORSELLI (2016: 76, fig. 17n-o).

Figure 15. *Parthenina brattstroemi* Warén, 1991 from DAI/02 AT800. A: shell (1.00 × 0.65 mm); B: detail of the sculpture of the teleoconch; C: protoconch.

Figura 15. *Parthenina brattstroemi* Warén, 1991 de DAI/02 AT800. A: concha (1,00 × 0,65 mm); B: detalle de la escultura de la teleoconcha; C: protoconcha.

Chrysallida interspatiosa van der Linden & Eikenboom, 1992: 21, figs. 10, 25-26.

Chrysallida (Parthenina) flexuosa (Monterosato) – VAN AARTSEN ET AL. (2000: 30).

Parthenina flexuosa (Monterosato) – GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL. (2014: figs. 155-157, appendix p. 67); APPOLLONI ET AL. (2018: 68, figs. 26Q-R); PEÑAS ET AL. (2019: 9); CABALLERO-HERRERA ET AL. (2023b: fig. 3N).

Material examined (1 empty shell): Spain • 1 sh; 43°51.873'N, 08°53.683'W to 43°53.120'N, 08°53.301'W; 802-788 m; 15 Sep. 2003; DAI/83 EBS-800.

Type locality: Palermo, Sicily (APPOLLONI ET AL., 2018).

Parthenina flexuosa is known off Azores, south Azorean and Josephine seamounts, Gulf of Cádiz and the Mediterranean in bathyal bottoms (PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 2011; GOFAS ET AL., 2014; NEGRI & CORSELLI,

2016; PEÑAS ET AL., 2019; UTRILLA ET AL., 2020; CABALLERO-HERRERA, 2023a, b) and was already reported from Galicia by ROLÁN (1983). Only one empty shell was found in a sample collected at 788-802 m.

Parthenina brattstroemi Warén, 1991 (Fig. 15)

Chrysallida brattstroemi Warén, 1991: 100, figs. 32A-C, 33D

Chrysallida brattstroemi Warén: MICALI ET AL. (1993: 153, fig. 7a-b); PEÑAS ET AL. (1996: 14-15, figs. 27-28).

Parthenina brattstroemi Warén: GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL. (2014: fig. 187, appendix p. 69); HØISÆTER (2014: 22, fig. 22); LANDAU & MICALI (2021: 258, plate 61, figs. 1-2).

Material examined (1 empty shell): Spain • 1 sh; 43°47.188'N, 08°53.053'W to 43°55.312'N, 08°53.101'W; 770-842 m; 11 Sep. 2002; DAI/02 AT-800.

Type locality: Skagerrak, 58°54'N - 10°33'E, 200-220 m (WARÉN, 1991).

Figure 16. *Parthenina* aff. *brattstroemi* Warén, 1991. A-D: shell (1.0 × 0.6 mm) from DAI/03 EBS-800, protoconch and its microsculpture; E, F: shell (1.1 × 0.6 mm) from DAI/02AT-1000 and its protoconch.

Figura 16. *Parthenina* aff. *brattstroemi* Warén, 1991. A-D: *concha* (1,0 × 0,6 mm) de DAI/03 EBS-800, *protoconcha* y su *microescultura*; E, F: *concha* (1,1 × 0,6 mm) de DAI/02AT-1000 y su *protoconcha*.

This species is only known from Norway (WARÉN, 1991; HØISÆTER (2014) and in few localities of the western and central Mediterranean in bathyal bottoms (MICALI *ET AL.*, 1993;

PEÑAS *ET AL.*, 1996; GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.*, 2014). The only shell studied was collected in a sample at 770-842 m. This is the first record in Spanish waters.

Figure 17. *Parthenina* cf. *palazzii* (Micali, 1984). A-C: shell from DAI/03 EBS-100 (1.6 × 0.75 mm), detail of its microsculpture and apical view of its protoconch; D, E: shell from VE/04 AG EBS-150 (2.1 × 0.9 mm) and detail of its microsculpture.

Figura 17. *Parthenina* cf. *palazzii* (Micali, 1984). A-C: concha de DAI/03 EBS-100 (1,6 × 0,75 mm), detalle de su microescultura y vista apical de su protoconcha; D, E: concha de VE/04 AG EBS-150 (2,1 × 0,9 mm) y detalle de su microescultura.

Parthenina aff. *brattstroemi* Warén, 1991 (Fig. 16)

Material examined (2 empty shells in 2 samples): Spain • 1 sh; 43°57.030'N, 08°54.795'W to 43°57.248'N, 08°54.133'W; 1191-1132 m; 9 Sep. 2002; DAI/02 AT-1000 • 1 sh; 43°51.873'N, 08°53.683'W to 43°53.120'N, 08°53.301'W; 802-788 m; 15 Sep. 2003; DAI/83 EBS-800).

The shells studied (collected in the depth range 788-1191 m) share characteristics of small northern *Parthenina* species of the group of *P. brattstroemi*, *P. hoisaeteri* Warén, 1991 and *P. eximia* (Jeffreys, 1849), being more similar to the first, but their protoconch is rough

(smooth in *P. brattstroemi* and *P. hoisaeteri*), like in *P. eximia* which is however much more slender in shape. ROLÁN (1983) reported *Chrysallida eximia* from Ría de Vigo based on a single shell, but that illustrated specimen is *Parthenina clathrata*.

Figure 18. *Eulimella scillae* (Scacchi, 1835) from SE/08 DRN15-2. A-E: shell (9.2 × 2.2 mm), protoconch, detail of the microsculpture of the teleoconch, and aperture.

Figura 18. Eulimella scillae (Scacchi, 1835) de SE/08 DRN15-2. A-E: concha (9,2 × 2,2 mm), protoconcha, detalle de la microescultura de la teleoconcha y abertura.

Parthenina cf. palazzii (Micali, 1984) (Fig. 17)

Chrysallida palazzii Micali, 1984: 246-247 – MICALI *ET AL.* (1983a: 150-151, fig. 6 holotype); PEÑAS *ET AL.* (1996: 26, figs. 32-33); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1998: 40, fig. 115); ÖZTÜRK *ET AL.* (2011: 72, fig. 18); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2011: 370); SCUDERI & TERLIZZI (2012: pl. 20, fig. 13).

Parthenina palazzii (Micali) – GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.* (2014: fig. 202, appendix p. 70); PEÑAS *ET AL.* (2014: 114, figs. 2H-J); CABALLERO-HERRERA *ET AL.* (2023b: figs. 3L-M).

Material examined (8 empty shells in 3 samples): Spain • 1 sh; 43°35.451'N, 08°34.432'W to 43°34.810'N, 08°35.407'W; 153-151 m; 14 Sep. 2002; DAI/02 EBS-150 • 7 sh; 43°26.703'N, 08°30.669'W to 43°27.452'N, 08°29.612'W; 102-103 m; 11 Sep. 2003; DA/03 EBS-100 • 2 sh; 43°31.970'N, 08°37.670'W to 43°32.697'N, 08°33.171'W; 151 m; 17 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-EBS-150.

Type locality: Imprecise place in the Middle Adriatic, about 60 m (MICALI, 1984).

Parthenina palazzii has been recorded in the Mediterranean and along the west African coasts as far as Guinea-Bissau, in circalittoral and upper bathyal bottoms (MICALI, 1984; PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 1998, 2011;

PEÑAS *ET AL.*, 2014; CABALLERO-HERRERA *ET AL.*, 2023b). The holotype of this species seems to be a juvenile (MICALI, 1984: 246) and the illustrated adult specimens from different areas show some variability, as

do the shells studied here (Fig. 17), found in samples collected between 102 and 153 m. We have identified these shells with doubt, but if the identification is con-

firmed, this would be the first record of this species on the European Atlantic coasts broadening its distribution area towards the north.

Genus *Eulimella* Forbes & McAndrew, 1846

Type species by original designation: *Eulima macandrei* Forbes, 1844, accepted as *Eulimella scillae* (Scacchi, 1835).

Eulimella scillae (Scacchi, 1835) (Fig. 18)

Melania scillae Scacchi, 1835: 11, pl. 2, fig. 2.

Eulimella scillae (Scacchi) – FRETTER *ET AL.* (1986: 624-625, figs. 434-435); WARÉN (1991: 110, figs. 37A, 38C); NOFRONI (1992: fig. 3); VAN AARTSEN (1994: 98, fig. 17); SCHANDER (1995: 62); PEÑAS *ET AL.* (1996: 34-36, figs. 66-68); ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (1999: 79); VAN AARTSEN *ET AL.* (2000: 3-4, figs. 1-2); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2011: 379); SCAPERROTTA *ET AL.* (2011: 110); SCUDERI & TERLIZZI (2012: pl. 20, fig. 3); ÖZTÜRK & BITLIS BAKIR (2013b: 427-428, fig. 8); HØISÆTER (2014: 59, figs. 99-100); GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.* (2014: fig. 305, appendix p. 83); NEGRI & CORSELLI (2016: 76-77, fig. 17h-j); LANDAU & MICALI (2021: 359-361, pl. 174, fig. 1).

Material examined (3 empty shells in 3 samples): Spain • 1 sh; 43°53.847'N, 08°57.324'W to 43°54.621'N, 08°57.261'W; 993-1004 m; 16 Sep. 2003; DAI/03 AT-1000 • 1 sh; 43°53.575'N, 08°56.868'W to 43°54.015'N, 08°56.959'W; 965-974 m; 16 Sep. 2003; DAIDRN-1000 • 1 sh; 43°56.478'N, 08°54.199'W to 43°55.934'N, 08°54.849'W; 620-933 m; 24 Jul. 2008; SE/08 DRN-15-2.

Type locality: Upper Pliocene, around Gravina di Puglia, southern Italy (WARÉN, 1991).

Eulimella scillae is distributed from northern Norway, Iceland and the Barents Sea to Azores, Madeira, Canary and Cape Verde islands, Gulf of Cádiz, Sahara, Mauritania, Guinea-Bissau, and the entire Mediterranean, from infralittoral to bathyal depths (FRETTER *ET AL.*, 1986; PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 2011, 2014; ÖZTÜRK &

BITLIS BAKIR, 2013; HØISÆTER, 2014; NEGRI & CORSELLI, 2016; BALLESTEROS *ET AL.*, 2019; CABALLERO-HERRERA *ET AL.* 2023b). Only three empty shells were found in the studied samples collected between 620 and 1004 m. This is apparently the first record in northern Spain, filling a gap in the known range of the species.

Eulimella neoattenuata Gaglini, 1992 (Fig. 19)

Eulimella neoattenuata Gaglini, 1992: 140-141, fig. 143.

Eulimella verduini van Aartsen, Gittenberger & Gould, 1998: 43, fig. 47.

Eulimella neoattenuata Gaglini – PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999: 163, figs. 29-31); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2011: 379); ÖZTÜRK & BITLIS BAKIR (2013b: 427, fig. 7); GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.* (2014: figs. 298-299, appendix p. 83); PEÑAS *ET AL.* (2014: 173-174 fig. 24C); LANDAU & MICALI (2021: 356-218, plate 169, fig. 1).

Material examined (3 shells, two with soft parts, in 3 samples): Spain • 1 sh; 44°11.652'N, 08°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 08°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; SE DRN-7 • 1 spc; 42°55.76'N, 09°44.04'W to 42°55.79'N, 09°44.57'W; 709-728 m; 28 Sep. 2008; DAII/08 EBS-25 • 1 spc; 42°35.26'N, 09°34.54'W to 42°35.79'N, 09°42.77'W; 995-1050 m; 29 Sep. 2008; DAII/08 EBS-31.

Type locality: Adventure Bank, Sicily Channel, 80-100 m.

This species is known from the Mediterranean, Mauritania, Canary and Selvagens Islands and in the South

Azorean Seamount, mainly in bathyal bottoms (PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 1999; PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 2011; ÖZTÜRK & BITLIS BAKIR,

Figure 19. *Eulimella neoattenuata* Gaglini, 1992, de DAI/08 EBS-25. A: shell (5.5 × 1.6 mm); B, C: apex and protoconch; D: detail of the subsutural rim; E: growth lines and subsutural groove.
 Figura 19. *Eulimella neoattenuata* Gaglini, 1992, de DAI/08 EBS-25. A: concha (5,5 × 1,6 mm); B, C: ápice y protoconcha; D: detalle del borde subsutural; E: líneas de crecimiento y surco subsutural.

2013b; PEÑAS *ET AL.*, 2014). It has been recorded in southern Spain by PEÑAS *ET AL.* (2006) as very abundant in coralligenous bottoms, by UTRILLA *ET AL.* (2020) in the Gulf of Cádiz, and by CABALLERO-HERRERA *ET AL.* (2023b) on the Chella

Bank, Alboran Sea. The two shells found with soft parts were collected deeper than 700 m. This record is the first one from northern Spain and extends the known distribution of *E. neoattenuata* northwards.

Eulimella artabrensis n. sp. (Fig. 20)

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Type material. *Holotype*: Spain • 1 specimen with soft parts (fig. 20C); 43°26.703'N, 08°30.669'W to 43°27.452'N, 08°29.612'W; 102-103 m; 11 Sep. 2003; DA/03 EBS-100; MNHS MHN USC-10156. *Paratypes*: 6 shells (fig. 20 A–B, D–G); same data as the holotype; MNCN 15.05/200554 • 6 shells; same data as the holotype; MNHN-IM-2012-25391.

Other material examined: Spain • 12 spc + 21 sh; same data as the holotype • 5 sh; 43°29.412'N, 08°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 08°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 25 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-AT-110.

Type locality: in front of the Artabro Gulf, continental shelf off NW Galicia (43°26.703'N, 08°30.669'W to 43°27.452'N, 08°29.612'W; 102-103 m).

Derivatio nominis: *artabrensis* refers to the fact that this species is described from off the Artabro Gulf.

Figure 20. *Eulimella artabrensis* n. sp. (DAI/03 EBS-100). A, B: shell (paratype, 1.3 × 0.4 mm) and protoconch; C: shell (holotype, 1.8 × 0.8 mm); D-G: shell (paratype, 1.3 × 0.4 mm), protoconch, detail of the suture and microsculpture of the teleoconch.

Figura 20. *Eulimella artabrensis* n. sp. (DAI/03 EBS-100). A, B: concha (paratipo, 1,3 × 0,4 mm) y protoconcha; C: concha (holotipo, 1,8 × 0,8 mm); D-G: concha (paratipo, 1,3 × 0,4 mm), protoconcha, detalle de la sutura y microscultura de la teleoconcha.

Description: Shell subcylindrical (Fig. 20A, C, D), tapering slowly to a blunt apex, and rounded base. Helicoid protoconch of the type A2, with a coiling axis perpendicular to the teleoconch axis (Fig. 20B, E) with three whorls, ranging between 230 and 260 µm in diameter. Dimension of holotype: 1.8 × 0.8 mm. Four to five planoconvex teleoconch whorls separated by a deep suture, with a flat subsutural rim (Fig. 20F). Oval aperture which occupies somewhat more than 25%

of the height of the shell. Columella curved and opisthoclinal. Delicate spiral microsculpture crossed by numerous orthoclinal growth lines which produce a fine surface reticulation (Fig. 20G).

Remarks: This new species resembles *Eulimella trewae* van Aartsen, Gittenberger & Goud, 2000, from which it can be distinguished by its subsutural rim (absent in *E. trewae*), and by its smaller protoconch (300-350 µm in *E. trewae*). In comparison to *Eulimella acicula*, the most

Figure 21. *Eulimella atlantis* Peñas & Rolán 1999, from SE/08 DRN7-3. A: shell (4.7 × 1.1 mm); B, C: apical view and protoconch; D: columella; E: suture.

Figura 21. *Eulimella atlantis* Peñas & Rolán 1999, de SE/08 DRN7-3. A: concha (4,7 × 1,1 mm); B, C: vista apical y protoconcha; D: columela; E: sutura.

common species of this genus in European coasts, the shells of *E. artabrensis* n. sp. are more clearly cylindrical, smaller, the microsculpture is much more pronounced, and the protoconch more protruding and has nearly one more whorl. The shell of *E. acicula* (Philippi, 1836) also lacks the subsutural rim that characterizes the new species.

Forty six shells and specimens of the new species were found in the same sample (collected at 102-103 m depth in muddy sand). In this sample were also found living specimens of *Megastomia conoidea*, *Brachystomia eulimoides*, *Odostomia acuta*, and *Liostomia afzelii*. Five additional shells of the new species were found in another sample at 110-111 m.

Eulimella atlantis Peñas & Rolán 1999 (Fig. 21)

Eulimella atlantis Peñas & Rolán, 1999: 156-157, figs. 11-13.

Material examined (2 empty shells in 2 samples): Spain • 1 sh; 43°36.544'N, 09°03.064'W to 43°36.816'N, 09°04.339'W; 601-619 m; 28 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-EBS-600 • 1 sh; 44°05.043'N, 08°57.977'W to 44°05.186'N, 08°57.821'W; 829-813 m; 20 Jul. 2008; SE/08 DRN-7-3.

Type locality: Atlantis Seamount, st. DW 274, 34°05,10'N - 30°13,60'W, 280 m.

This species is only known from the type locality in the south Azorean seamounts. The teleoconch and protoconch of the two shells here studied (found in the depth range 601-829 m)

matches with the species described by PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999b). The present record is the second of the species, it is new for Spanish waters and extends its distribution area to the European slope.

Eulimella cerullii (Cossmann, 1915) (Figs. 22, 24C-D)

Syrnola cerullii Cossmann, 1915: 60 (new name for *Odostomia praelonga* Jeffreys, 1886: 350, pl. 26, fig. 6).

Eulimella cerullii (Cossmann) – VAN AARTSEN (1994: 101, fig. 20); PEÑAS ET AL. (1996: 34, figs. 64-65); GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL. (2014: fig. 296, appendix p. 83)

Material examined (12 shells, 2 with soft parts, in 5 samples): Spain • 2 spc + 5 sh; 43°48.587'N, 08°51.402'W to 43°49.545'N, 08°51.197'W; 598-610 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DAI/03 EBS-600 • 1 sh; 44°06.943'N, 08°47.232'W to 44°07.173'N, 08°46.031'W; 440-429 m; 17 Jul. 2008; SE/08 EBS-11-2 • 4 sh; 44°09.896'N, 08°39.581'W to 44°10.129'N, 08°39.494'W; 438-459 m; 18 Jul. 2008; SE/08 DRN-11 • 1 sh; 44°08.65'N, 08°55.305'W to 44°08.771'N, 08°55.104'W; 581-566 m; 20 Jul. 2008; SE/08 DRN-7C • 1 spc; 42°55.76'N, 09°44.04'W to 42°55.79'N, 09°44.57'W; 709-728 m; 28 Sep. 2008; DAII/08 EBS-25.

Type locality: Not designated. Jeffreys (1886) described *O. praelonga* from various stations of the Porcupine Expeditions in the Mediterranean and nearby Atlantic.

This species is known from the Bay of Biscay to off northwestern Africa and in the central and the western Mediterranean, down to 2651 m (LOCARD, 1897; PEÑAS ET AL., 1996; GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI

ET AL., 2014; SYSOEV, 2014; CABALLERO-HERRERA ET AL., 2023b). Twelve shells were found in samples collected in the depth range 429-728 m, two of them with soft parts in a sample at 598-610 m.

Eulimella sp. 1 (Figs. 23, 24E-F)

Material examined (7 empty shells in 4 samples): Spain • 1 sh; 44°11.652'N, 08°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 08°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; SE/08 DRN-7 • 4 sh (3 juv); 44°08.65'N, 08°55.305'W to 44°08.771'N, 08°55.104'W; 581-566 m; 20 Jul. 2008; SE/08 DRN-7C • 1 sh (juv); 43°24.64'N, 09°31.56'W to 43°25.38'N, 09°30.97'W; 880-814 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DAII/08 DRNp3-08 • 1 sh; 43°16.50'N, 09°34.52'W to 43°16.71'N, 09°33.79'W; 565-503 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DAII/08 DRNr-18.

Seven shells (3 of them juveniles) were similar to *E. cerulli* (see Figure 24 for comparison), but their size is somewhat larger (up to 5.5 mm, up to 4.8 in *E. cerullii*), whorls slightly convex with a subsutural ridge, and protoconch of type B wider than the first whorls.

These shells were found in the depth range 503-1106 m, their microsculpture looks somewhat different (Fig. 23 E, G), but their protoconchs are identical, including the adapical groove on initial teleoconch whorl. It may also be a new species.

(Right page) Figure 22. *Eulimella cerullii* (Cossmann, 1915). A-C: shell (4.8 mm) from DAI/03 EBS-600, aperture and detail of the subsutural microsculpture; D-F: shell (4.0 mm) from DAII/08 EBS-25, protoconch and detail of the microsculpture; G, H: shell (4.7 mm) from SE/08 DRN-11 and protoconch; I, J: shell (4.5 mm) from SE/08 DRN-11 and protoconch; K: juvenile shell (2.2 mm) from SE/08 DRN-7C.

Figura 22. *Eulimella cerullii* (Cossmann, 1915). A-C: concha (4,8 mm) de DAI/03 EBS-600, abertura y detalle de la microescultura subsutural; D-F: concha (4,0 mm) de DAII/08 EBS-25, protoconcha y detalle de la microescultura; G, H: concha (4,7 mm) de SE/08 DRN-11 y protoconcha; I, J: concha (4,5 mm) de SE/08 DRN-11 y protoconcha; K: concha juvenil (2,2 mm) de SE/08 DRN-7C.

Figure 23. *Eulimella* sp 1. A, B: shell (4.9×1.3 mm) from SE/08 DRN7-C, and detail of its columellar fold; C-E: shell (5.5×1.4 mm) from SE/08 DRN7, protoconch and detail of the microsculpture of the teleoconch; F-H: shell (5.5×1.4 mm), protoconch and detail of the subsutural ridge, SE/08 DRN7; I: shell (4.7×1.4 mm) from DAII/08 DRNr-18.

Figura 23. *Eulimella* sp 1. A, B: concha ($4,9 \times 1,3$ mm) de SE/08 DRN7-C, y detalle de su pliegue columelar; C-E: concha ($5,5 \times 1,4$ mm) de SE/08 DRN7, protoconcha y detalle de la microescultura de la teleoconcha; F-H: concha ($5,5 \times 1,4$ mm), protoconcha y detalle de la cresta subsutural, SE/08 DRN7; I: concha ($4,7 \times 1,4$ mm) de DAII/08 DRNr-18.

Eulimella ventricosa (Forbes, 1844) (Figs. 25-26)

Parthenia ventricosa Forbes, 1844: 188.

Eulimella gracilis Jeffreys, 1847: 311.

Eulimella gracilis Jeffreys – RODRÍGUEZ BABÍO & THIRIOT-QUIÉVREUX (1974: 70, pl. 6 figs. B, F protoconch).

Figura 24. Comparison of shells to scale and their protoconchs. A, B: *Eulimella cerullii* off Cádiz (3.8 × 1.2 mm); C, D: *Eulimella cerulli* from DAI/03 EBS-600 (4.0 × 1.2 mm); E, F: *Eulimella* sp. 1 from SE/08 DRN-7 (5.5 × 1.4 m).

Figura 24. Comparación de conchas a escala y sus protoconchas. A, B: *Eulimella cerullii* del Golfo de Cádiz (3,8 × 1,2 mm); C, D: *Eulimella cerulli* de DAI/03 EBS-600 (4,0 × 1,2 mm); E, F: *Eulimella* sp. 1 de SE/08 DRN-7 (5,5 × 1,4 m).

Eulimella ventricosa (Forbes) – VAN AARTSEN *ET AL.* (1984: 50, 123, fig. 242); FRETTER *ET AL.* (1986: 627-628, figs. 437); WARÉN (1991: 111, fig. 37B); VAN AARTSEN (1994: 100, 109, fig. 21); SCHANDER (1995: 61, fig. 1A); PEÑAS *ET AL.* (1996: 38, figs. 72-73, 77); GIRIBET & PEÑAS (1997: 76: fig. 73); ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (1999: 79); VAN AARTSEN *ET AL.* (2000: 10, figs. 11-12 as *E. ventricosa* var.); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2011: 377); SCAPERROTTA *ET AL.* (2011: 111); SCUDERI & TERLIZZI (2012: pl. 20, fig. 5); ÖZTÜRK & BITLIS BAKIR (2013b: 428, fig. 9); HOISÆTER (2014: 60, figs. 96, 101-102); GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.* (2014: figs. 301-304, appendix p. 83); PEÑAS *ET AL.* (2014: 178, figs. 24M-N); LANDAU & MICALI (2021: 362-363, pl. 177, figs. 1-2).

Material examined (21 shells, 1 with soft parts, in 11 samples): Spain • 2 sh; 43°57.030'N, 08°54.795'W to 43°57.248'N, 08°54.133'W; 1191-1132 m; 9 Sep. 2002; DAI/02 AT-1000 • 2 sh (juv); 43°47.188'N, 08°53.053'W to 43°55.312'N, 08°53.101'W; 770-842 m; 11 Sep. 2002; DAI/02 AT-800 • 1 spc; 43°51.873'N, 08°53.683'W to 43°53.120'N, 08°53.301'W; 802-788 m; 15 Sep. 2003; DAI/03 EBS-800 • 1 sh; 43°48.421'N, 08°51.453'W to 43°49.160'N, 08°51.091'W; 599-607 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DAI DRN-600 • 1 sh (juv); 43°38.812'N, 09°07.949'W to 43°39.841'N, 09°07.405'W; 999-1001 m; 28 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-DRN-1000 • 1 sh; polygon delimited by points 44°10'N, 09°00'W / 44°10'N, 08°35'W / 44°00'N, 09°00'W / 44°07'N; 08°35'W; 480-600 m; 19 Apr. 2007; SA/07-2 • 1 sh; polygon delimited by points 44°10.00'N, 09°00.00'W / 44°10.00'N, 08°35.00'W / 44°00.00'N, 09°00.00'W / 44°07.00'N, 08°35.00'W; 417-668 m; 15 Jul. 2007; SA/07-3 • 2 sh (juv); polygon delimited by points 44°10'N, 09°00'W / 44°10'N, 08°35'W / 44°00'N, 09°00'W / 44°07'N, 08°35'W; 417-668 m; 1 Aug. 2007; SA/07-4 • 1 sh; polygon delimited by points 44°10'N, 09°00'W / 44°10'N, 08°35'W / 44°00'N, 09°00'W / 44°07'N, 08°35'W; 480-600 m; 12 Nov. 2007; SA/07-5 • 2 sh; 44°06.943'N, 08°47.232'W to 44°07.173'N, 08°46.031'W; 440-429 m; 17 Jul. 2008; SE/08 EBS-11-2 • 1 sh; 44°07.495'N, 08°46.99'W to 44°07.675'N, 08°45.225'W; 416-407 m; 18 Jul. 2008; SE/08 AT-11-2 • 5 sh; 43°34.86'N, 09°21.95'W to 43°36.44'N, 09°20.71'W; 1010-1112 m; 19 Sep. 2008; DAI/08 EBS-04.

Type locality: “Cerigo” [Kythira], Greece, and Lycia, SW Turkey (Aegean Sea).

Figure 25. *Eulimella ventricosa* (Forbes, 1844). A, B: shell (2.3 × 0.7mm) from DAI/08 EBS-04 and apex; C-F: shell (2.2 × 0.7 mm) from DAI/08 EBS-04, protoconch, detail of its suture and growth lines; G: protoconch of another shell from SE/08 DRN-11.

Figura 25. Eulimella ventricosa (Forbes, 1844). A, B: concha (2,3 × 0,7 mm) de DAI/08 EBS-04 y ápice; C-F: concha (2,2 × 0,7 mm) de DAI/08 EBS-04, protoconcha, detalle de su sutura y líneas de crecimiento; G: protoconcha de otra concha de SE/08 DRN-11.

Eulimella ventricosa is a very common species widely distributed geographically and bathymetrically. It is known from Southern Barents Sea, Iceland and Northern Norway (SARS, 1878; FRIELE & GRIEG; 1901; WARÉN, 1991; SCHANDER, 1995; HØISÆTER, 2014), southwards to Guinea-Bissau (PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 2014), including Madeira, Canary and Cape Verde islands (VAN AARTSEN ET AL., 2000; PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 2014), and the whole Mediter-

ranean (PEÑAS ET AL., 1996; SCAPERROTTA ET AL., 2011; ÖZTÜRK & BITLIS BAKIR, 2013b; GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL., 2014), in the depth range 50-1000 m. It is quite common in the seamounts and banks of the Alboran Sea (PEÑAS ET AL., 2006; GOFAS ET AL., 2014; CABALLERO-HERRERA ET AL., 2023b). This species belongs to a group of species of this genus characterized by their fragility, convex whorl profile, moderate deep suture and columella without fold.

Figure 26. *Eulimella ventricosa* (Forbes, 1844). A-C: shell (4.4 × 1.1 mm) from DAII/08 EBS-04, microsculpture and apex; D, E: shell (1.9 × 0.6 mm) and its protoconch from SE/08 EBS 11-2; F: protoconch of another shell from DA/03 AT-800.

Figura 26. *Eulimella ventricosa* (Forbes, 1844). A-C: concha (4,4 × 1,1 mm) de DAII/08 EBS-04, microsculptura y ápice; D, E: concha (1,9 × 0,6 mm) y su protoconcha de SE/08 EBS 11-2; F: protoconcha de otra concha de DA/03 AT-800.

The type material of this taxon described by FORBES (1844) from shells from the Aegean Sea is not found. VAN AARTSEN (1994) interprets the species by selecting and illustrating a specimen from Palermo in the British Museum with a handwritten label of MONTEROSATO, and WARÉN (1991) and HØISÆTER (2014) also discuss the taxonomic complexity of this variable species. VAN AARTSEN *ET AL.* (2000) refer as *E. ventricosa* var. some shells from Cape Verde Islands, and ÖZTÜRK & BITLİS BAKIR (2013) illustrated

two shells from the Turkish Aegean Sea collected at different depths that show different convexity of their whorls. Molecular studies are necessary to elucidate whether this taxon includes a complex of cryptic species. We maintain the name *Eulimella ventricosa* for those shells with a clearly convex whorl profile and a uniform growth rate. *Eulimella similebala* Peñas & Rolán, 1999 is similar to *E. ventricosa* (which is more cylindrical) but shows a subsutural groove, absent in the latter.

Figure 27. *Eulimella* cf. *ataktos* Warén, 1991. A, B: shell (1.5 × 0.7 mm) from SE/08 EBS-11 and details of the growth lines; C, D: protoconch of another shell from VE/04 GA-EBS-600 and detail. *Figura 27. Eulimella* cf. *ataktos* Warén, 1991. A, B: concha (1,5 × 0,7 mm) de SE/08 EBS-11 y detalles de las líneas de crecimiento; C, D: protoconcha de otra concha de VE/04 GA-EBS-600 y detalle.

Two forms have been observed among the shells regarding the profile of the whorls (see figs. 25 and 26 for comparison). The only living specimen was found in a sample collected at 788-802 m

depth. The empty shells come from samples collected between 416 and 1191 m. This is the first record from northern Spain, filling a gap in the known distribution.

Eulimella cf. *ataktos* Warén, 1991 (Fig. 27)

Eulimella ataktos Warén, 1991: 114, figs. 37b, 38e.

Eulimella ataktos Warén – SCHANDER (1995: 62); PEÑAS ET AL. (1996: 33, figs. 70-71, 76); GIRIBET & PEÑAS (1997: 76, fig. 72); HØISÆTER (2014: 57, figs. 95-96).

Material examined (3 shells, 2 with soft parts, in 2 samples): Spain • 1 spc; 43°36.544'N, 09°03.064'W to 43°36.816'N, 09°04.339'W; 601-619 m; 28 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-EBS-600 • 1 spc + 1 sh (juv); 44° 08.516'N, 08°40.788'W to 44° 09.688'N, 08°39.721'W; 436-428 m; 17 Jul. 2008; SE/08 EBS-11.

Type locality: Grøtsund, Troms, Northern Norway, 142-182 m.

This species is only known from Norway, Faeroes (WARÉN, 1991; SCHANDER, 1995; HØISÆTER, 2014) and the north-eastern Mediterranean, in circalittoral bottoms (PEÑAS ET AL., 1996; GIRIBET & PEÑAS, 1997), but it may have been previously confused with *E. ventricosa* due to its close similarity. The three shells examined (one of them with soft parts) best match

with *E. ataktos*, which differs conchologically from *E. ventricosa* in being broader. HØISÆTER (2014) wrote: “The question of whether *E. ataktos* is a valid species or only an extreme variety of *E. ventricosa* is still open”. Our specimens were found in samples collected at 436-428 m and 601-616 m, and would be the first record of this species for northern Spain.

Figure 28. *Eulimella* sp. 2. A: shell (2.2 × 0.8 mm) from SE/08 EBS-13; B, C: juvenile shell (1.3 × 0.5 mm) from DAI/02 AT-1000 and apex; D-F: protoconch of A, detail and suture.

Figura 28. Eulimella sp. 2. A: concha (2,2 × 0,8 mm) de SE/08 EBS-13; B, C: concha juvenil (1,3 × 0,5 mm) de DAI/02 AT-1000 y ápice; D-F: protoconcha de A, detalle y sutura.

Eulimella sp. 2 (Fig. 28)

Three shells (one of them with soft parts) collected in the depth range 337-1191 m, belong to the group of species

around *Eulimella ventricosa*, but the scarcity of specimens does not allow us to identify them with certainty.

Figura 29. *Turbonilla magnifica* Seguenza, 1880, from SE/08 DRN-7. A-C: shell (6.9 × 2.1 mm) and detail of its microsculpture. D, E: shell (5.7 × 1.2 mm) and protoconch.

Figura 29. *Turbonilla magnifica* Seguenza, 1880, de SE/08 DRN-7. A-C: concha (6,9 × 2,1 mm) y detalle de su microescultura. D, E: concha (5,7 × 1,2 mm) y protoconcha.

Genus *Turbonilla* Risso, 1826

Type species by subsequent designation: *Turbonilla costulata* Risso, 1826.

Turbonilla magnifica Seguenza, 1880 (Fig. 29)

Turbonilla magnifica Seguenza, 1880: 264-265, pl. 16, fig. 25.

Turbonilla magnifica Seguenza – JEFFREYS (1884: 357); LOCARD (1897: 437); VAN AARTSEN (1981: pl. 3, fig. 13 p. 84); PEÑAS ET AL. (1996: 70, fig. 176); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1997: 30-32); ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (1999: 80); GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL. (2014: fig. 253, appendix, p. 77)

Material examined (15 empty shells, in 7 samples): Spain • 1 sh (juv); 43°57.030'N, 08°54.795'W to 43°57.248'N, 08°54.133'W; 1191-1132 m; 9 Sep. 2002; DAI/02 AT-1000 • 7 sh; 44°11.652'N, 08°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 08°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; SE DRN-7 • 2 sh; 44°08.461'N, 09°04.634'W to 44°08.607'N, 09°04.413'W; 917-896 m; 20 Jul. 2008; SE/06 DRN-7-1 • 2 sh (juv); 44°08.65'N, 08° 55.305'W to 44°08.771'N, 08°55.104'W; 581-566 m; 20 Jul. 2008; SE/08 DRN-7C • 1 sh; 43°56.51'N, 08°49.869'W to 43°57.448'N, 08°749'W; 781-839 m; 21 Jul. 2008; SE/08 DRN-16-1 • 1 sh; 43°56.478'N, 08°54.199'W to 43°55.934'N, 08°54.849'W; 620-933 m; 24 Jul. 2008; SE/08 DRN-15-2 • 1 sh; 43°55.886'N, 08°54.846'W to 43°55.291'N, 08°55.65'W; 933-930 m; 24 Jul. 2008; SE/06 DRN-15-2b.

Type locality: Gallina, Reggio Calabria, Italia (bathyal, Pleistocene).

Figure 30. *Turbonilla* sp. 1 from VE/04 AG EBS-150. A: shell (2.1 × 0.6 mm); B: protoconch; C: aperture; D, E: details of the sculpture and microsculpture of the teleoconch.

Figura 30. *Turbonilla* sp. 1 de VE/04 AG EBS-150. A: concha (2,1 × 0,6 mm); B: protoconcha; C: abertura; D, E: detalles de la escultura y microescultura de la teleoconcha.

Turbonilla magnifica has been recorded from the Azores, Cape Verde Island, Gulf of Cádiz and the Mediterranean (LOCARD, 1897; GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.*, 2014; GOFAS *ET AL.*, 2014; UTRILLA *ET AL.*, 2020; CABALLERO-HERRERA *ET AL.* 2023a) in bathyal bottoms, following a lead by JEFFREYS (1884). However, the original figure in SEGUENZA (1880) shows a quite different shell and finding the correct name for the present figure needs further research. *Turbonilla magnifica* was recorded from Ría de Vigo by ROLÁN

(1983: 328) and from there included for the northern demarcation in the Spanish checklist (GOFAS *ET AL.*, 2017) but the shell figured is another species, possibly *T. pusilla* (Philippi, 1844). The older record from “Vigo” (quoting McAndrew) by JEFFREYS (1884) is not documented by any material and is unconfirmed. All the shells studied, found in samples in the depth range 566 y 1191 m, were old and eroded, which could be subfossil, therefore we refrain from presenting this as a new record.

Turbonilla sp. 1 (Fig. 30)

Material examined (15 empty shells, in 7 samples): Spain • 3 sh (juv); 43°26.703'N, 08°30.669'W to 43°27.452'N, 08°29.612'W; 102-103 m; 11 Sep. 2003; DAI/03 EBS-100 • 1 sh; 42°30.391'N, 09°19.517'W to 42°29.428'N, 09°17.924'W; 147-148m; 17 Sep. 2004; VE/04 AG EBS-150 • 3 sh; 43°29.13'N, 08°42.233'W to 43°29.596'N, 08°42.838'W; 149-151 m; 22 Jul. 2008; SE/08 DRN 22.

Fifteen shells examined (from seven samples collected between 102-151 m) resemble the descriptions and figures of *T. fulgidula* (Jeffreys, 1884) (VAN AARTSEN, 1981: pl. 1, fig. 3; BELLOCQ & NOFRONI, 1989: 232, figs. 8-9; SCHANDER, 1994: fig. 7g; PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 1997: 38, figs. 67-72; GIANNUZZI-

SAVELLI ET AL., 2014: figs. 242-243), but they have punctate incisions aligned spirally all over the entire surface instead of fine striations, like in *T. pseudomartelli* Peñas & Rolán, 1997 from west African coasts. This latter species has less prominent ribs and is somewhat larger.

Turbonilla sp. 2 (Fig. 31)

Material examined (13 shells, 7 with soft parts, in 3 samples): Spain • 3 sh; 43°26.703'N, 08°30.669'W to 43°27.452'N, 08°29.612'W; 102-103 m; 11 Sep. 2003; DAI/03 EBS-100 • 7 spc + 2 sh; 42°30.391'N, 09°19.517'W to 42°29.428'N, 09°17.924'W; 147-148 m; 17 Sep. 2004; VE/04 AG EBS-150 • 3 sh; 43°29.412'N, 08°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 08°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 25 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-AT-110.

Several of the studied shells (some with soft parts) were also similar to *Turbonilla pseudomartelli* Peñas y Rolán 1997, but they differ in their smaller size, smaller protoconch, and non-uniformly rounded body-whorl (Fig. 31A, C, G). These shells were small (up to 2.6 × 0.7 mm), subcylindrical, with six teleoconch whorls of flat profile. Their sculpture consists of weak, broad, straight, orthocone axial ribs, about 12 on penultimate whorl, somewhat wider than their interspaces. Spiral microsculpture consists of irregular incisions (Fig. 31E-F) somewhat diffe-

rent from the aligned punctures of *Turbonilla* sp. 1. The last whorl is 40% of total height, somewhat angular at the periphery. The base is smooth, the aperture subovate, well rounded anteriorly, 23% of total height. Protoconch is helicoidal of the type A1 (Fig. 31H), 260 μm width. They were collected between 102 and 148 m depth (living specimens at 147-148 m). *Turbonilla* sp. 2 is distinguished from the shells called *Turbonilla* sp. 1 by the flatter profile of its whorls, and by less prominent ribs, most closely set on the first teleoconch whorl.

Turbonilla hamonvillei Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896 (Fig. 32)

Turbonilla hamonvillei Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896: 471-472; pl. 20 fig. 3.

Turbonilla hamonvillei Dautzenberg & Fischer – PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999: 180-182, figs. 72-76), PEÑAS ET AL. (2019: 18, 20).

Material examined (2 empty shells, in 2 samples): Spain • 1 sh (juv); 44°11.652'N, 08°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 08°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; SE DRN-7 • 1 sh; 42°29.545'N, 10°10.502'W to 42°30.776'N, 10°09.651'W; 2765-2798 m; 15 Feb. 2009; FO/09 EBS-4.

Type locality: Off Azores, 38°33'21"N -30°28'54"W, 1300 m.

This species was only known from off Azores and on Atlantis and Josephine seamounts (PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 1999; PEÑAS ET AL., 2019). Here its distribution is

expanded to the area here studied, being the first record in Spanish waters. Only two empty shells were found in samples collected between 908 and 2798 m.

Turbonilla multilirata (Monterosato, 1875) (Fig. 33)

Odostomia (*Turbonilla*) *multilirata* Monterosato, 1875: 33.

Figure 31. *Turbonilla* sp. 2. A, B: shell (2.6×0.7 mm) from VE/04 AG EBS-150, and protoconch; C-F: shell (2.1×0.6 mm), protoconch and details of microsculpture of teleoconch, same locality; G, H: shell (2.0×0.6 mm) and protoconch, same locality; I: juvenile shell from DAI/03 EBS-100. *Figura 31.* *Turbonilla* sp. 2. A, B: concha ($2,6 \times 0,7$ mm) de VE/04 AG EBS-150, y protoconcha; C-F: concha ($2,1 \times 0,6$ mm), protoconcha y detalles de microescultura de la teleoconcha, misma localidad; G, H: concha ($2,0 \times 0,6$ mm) y protoconcha, misma localidad; I: concha juvenil de DAI/03 EBS-100.

Figure 32. *Turbonilla hamonvillei* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896. A: apical part of a broken shell from FO/09 EBS-4; B: protoconch; C: sculpture of the teleoconch; D: suture; E, F: juvenile shell (2.1 × 1.0 mm) from SE/08 DRN-7 and protoconch.

Figura 32. *Turbonilla hamonvillei* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896. A: parte apical de una concha rota de FO/09 EBS-4; B: protoconcha; C: escultura de la teleoconcha; D: sutura; E, F: concha juvenil (2,1 × 1,0 mm) de SE/08 DRN-7 y protoconcha.

Turbonilla multilirata (Monterosato) – VAN AARTSEN (1981: 75); GAGLINI (1992: 140-141, fig. 149); MICALI & MIFSUD (1992: 30-31, fig. 3); PEÑAS *ET AL.* (1996: 68, figs. 152-153); ENGL *ET AL.* (2009: 120, figs. 48-49); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2011: 395); SCAPERROTTA *ET AL.* (2011: 95); GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.* (2014: fig. 256, appendix p. 78); APPOLLONI *ET AL.* (2018: 70, figs. 27Q-R); LANDAU & MICALI (2021: 336, plate 143, fig. 1).

Material examined (4 empty shells in 3 samples): Spain • 1 sh; 43°48.421'N, 08°51.453'W to 43°49.160'N, 08°51.091'W; 599-607 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DAI DRN-600 • 1 sh; 43°48.587'N, 08°51.402'W to 43°49.545'N, 08°51.197'W; 598-610 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DAI/03 EBS-600 • 2 sh; 44°09.896'N, 08°39.581'W to 44°10.129'N, 08°39.494'W; 438-459 m; 18 Jul. 2008; SE/08 DRN-11.

Type locality: Palermo, Sicily, 60-90 m (APPOLLONI *ET AL.*, 2018).

This species is known in the Atlantic, from the Ibero-Moroccan Gulf and Canary Islands, and in the western and central Mediterranean, in infralittoral and circalittoral bottoms (MICALI & MIFSUD, 1992; ENGL *ET AL.*, 2009;

PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 2011). Four shells were found in samples collected between 437 and 610 m. This record is the first one for northern Spain and expands northwards the known range of the species.

Figure 33. *Turbonilla multilirata* (Monterosato, 1875) from SE/08 DRN-11. A-D: shell (5.5 × 1.6 mm), protoconch and details of the sculpture.

Figura 33. *Turbonilla multilirata* (Monterosato, 1875) de SE/08 DRN-11. A-D: concha (5,5 × 1,6 mm), protoconcha y detalles de la escultura.

Genus *Pyrgiscus*

Type species by subsequent designation: *Melania rufa* Philippi, 1836.

Pyrgiscus crenatus (Brown, 1827) (Fig. 34)

Pyramis crenatus Brown, 1827: pl. 50, fig. 53.

Turritella fulvocincta Thompson, 1840: 98.

Turbonilla crenata (Brown) – RODRÍGUEZ BABÍO & THIRIOT-QUIÉVREUX (1975: 501, pl. 2 figs. A-C);

FRETTER *ET AL.* (1986: 638-639, figs. 445-446); BECK *ET AL.* (2006: 86); PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2011: 396).

Pyrgiscus fulvocinctus Thompson: HØISÆTER (2014: 66-67, figs. 109-110).

Pyrgiscus crenatus Brown: GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.* (2014: figs. 276-277, 280, appendix p. 80).

Material examined (21 shells, 3 with soft parts, in 6 samples): Spain • 1 spc; 43°40.192'N, 08°43.760'W to 43°40.943'N, 08°42.366'W; 207-212 m; 8 sept. 2002; DA/02 ESB-200 • 3 sh (juv); 43°26.703'N, 08°30.669'W to 43°27.452'N, 08°29.612'W; 102-103 m; 11 Sep. 2003; DAI/03 EBS-100 • 1 spc + 1 sh; 43°31.970'N, 08°37.670'W to 43°32.697'N, 08°37.171'W; 151 m; 17 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-EBS-150 • 1 sh (juv); 42°29.455'N, 09°17.472'W to 42°31.292'N, 09°19.660'W; 147-149 m; 19 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-AT-150 • 3 sh (juv); 43°29.412'N, 08°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 08°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 25 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-AT-110 • 1 spc; 43°33.20'N, 08°58.78'W to 43°34.57'N, 08°56.90'W; 230-236 m; 16 Sep. 2008; DAII/08 EBS-01.

Type locality: Not known. Type locality of *P. fulvicinctus*: Portmarnock, near Dublin.

Pyrgiscus crenatus has sometimes been synonymised with *Pyrgiscus rufus*

(Philippi, 1836) (e.g. VAN AARTSEN, 1981) and PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2011) also stated

Figure 34. *Pyrgiscus crenatus* (Brown, 1827). A-C: juvenile shell (2.1 × 0.7 mm) from DAI/03 EBS-100, protoconch and microsulpture; D, E: juvenile shell (2.2 × 0.7 mm) from VE/04 GA AT-110 and basal part; F: protoconch of another shell from DAI/03 EBS-100.

Figura 34. *Pyrgiscus crenatus* (Brown, 1827). A-C: concha juvenil (2,1 × 0,7 mm) de DAI/03 EBS-100, protoconcha y microescultura; D, E: concha juvenil (2,2 × 0,7 mm) de VE/04 GA AT-110 y parte basal; F: protoconcha de otra concha de DAI/03 EBS-100.

that both taxa may be extreme morphotypes of the same species. This species distributes from Norway to the Sahara, including Canaries, Madeira and Seine Seamount, and the western and central Mediterranean in a wide depth range (FRETTER *ET AL.*, 1986; BECK *ET AL.*, 2006;

PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 2011; GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.*, 2014; HØISÆTER, 2014). URGORRI & BESTEIRO (1983) recorded it in Galicia at 60 m. Several shells were found in samples collected in the depth range 102-236 m, three of them with soft parts in the deepest sample.

Pyrgiscus sp. (Fig. 35)

Material examined (4 shells, 1 with soft parts, in 1 sample): Spain • 1 spc + 3 sh (juv); 43°26.703'N, 08°30.669'W to 43°27.452'N, 08°29.612'W; 102-103 m; 11 Sep. 2003; DAI/03 EBS-100.

We have identified as *Pyrgiscus* sp. four of the shells studied (three of them juveniles and an adult with soft parts), found in a sample collected on a sandy-muddy bottom at 102-103 m depth. The only adult shell found is pinkish in colour, cyrtocoid outline with planoconvex whorls and orthocline ribs narrower than their interspaces (Fig. 35A).

The entire surface is covered by non-equidistant spiral grooves of variable width, visible only in the interspaces (Fig. 36F). In the penultimate whorl there are five grooves of different widths. At the base of the shell there are 5-6 continuous grooves narrower than the interspaces (Fig. 36C). Protoconch is of type A-1 tending towards B (Fig. 36B, E).

Figure 35. *Pyrgiscus* sp. from DAI/03 EBS-100. A-C: shell (4.2 × 1.1 mm), protoconch and basal part; D-F: juvenile shell (1.5 × 0.6 mm), protoconch and microsculpture of the teleoconch.

Figura 35. *Pyrgiscus* sp. de DAI/03 EBS-100. A-C: concha (4,2 × 1,1 mm), protoconcha y parte basal; D-F: concha juvenil (1,5 × 0,6 mm), protoconcha y microescultura de la teleoconcha.

Pyrgiscus mediocris (Peñas & Rolán 1999) n. comb. (Fig. 36)

Turbonilla mediocris Peñas & Rolán, 1999: 186-189, figs. 88-96 – PEÑAS *ET AL.* (2019: 20).

Material examined (1 empty shell): Spain • 1 sh; 44°11.652'N, 08°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 08°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; SE DRN-7.

Type locality: Great Meteor Seamount, DW 152 (30°02.0'N, 28°22.1'W), 470 m.

Previously only known from the south Azorean and Josephine seamounts in the depth range 460-890 m (PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 1999b; PEÑAS *ET AL.*, 2019). Here its distribution is expanded to off continental European coast. Only

one empty shell was found in a sample collected at 908-1106 m. The present record is the first one for Spanish waters and extends the known distribution of *P. mediocris* to the European continental slope.

Figure 36. *Pyrgiscus mediocris* (Peñas & Rolán 1999) from SE/08 DRN-7. A-E: shell (6.5 × 1.7 mm), protoconch, basal part, sculpture and microsculpture.

Figura 36. *Pyrgiscus mediocris* (Peñas & Rolán 1999) de SE/08 DRN-7. A-E: concha (6,5 × 1,7 mm), protoconcha, parte basal, escultura y microescultura

Coastal species represented by few shells (considered accidental in the bottoms sampled, probably swept by currents)

Odostomella doliolum (Philippi, 1844) (Fig. 37A)

Material examined: only one empty shell was found in the sample DAI/03 EBS-100 at 102-103 m. It is juvenile, but the characteristic coloured lines are visible. This is the first record for northern Spain and expands northwards the known distribution.

Folinella excavata (Philippi, 1836) (Fig. 37B)

Material examined: two empty shells was found in the sample VE04 GA-AT110 at 110-111 m.

Parthenina monozona (Brusina, 1869) (Fig. 37D)

Material examined: six empty shells in the samples DAI/03 EBS-100 (at 102-103 m) and VE/04 GA-AT-110 (at 110-111 m). This species was recorded from Galicia by Rolán (1983) under the name *Chrysallida intermixta* (Monterosato, 1884), currently considered a synonym.

Parthenina terebellum (Philippi, 1844) (Fig. 37I)

Material examined: one empty shell found in the sample DAI DRN-600 collected around 600 m depth.

Parthenina decussata (Montagu, 1803) (Fig. 37C)

Material examined: six empty shells in the sample VE/04 GA-AT-110 at 110-111 m.

Parthenina indistincta (Montagu, 1803) (Fig. 37H)

Material examined: two empty shells in the samples VE/04 GA-EBS-150 and VE/04 GA-AT-150 collected around 150 m depth.

Odostomia lukisii Jeffreys, 1859 (Fig. 38A)

Material examined: only one empty shell was found in the sample VE04 GA-AT110 at 110-111 m.

Odostomia plicata (Montagu, 1803) (Fig. 38C)

Material examined: only one empty shell was found in the sample VE04 GA-AT110 at 110-111 m.

Odostomia turrita Hanley, 1844 (Fig. 38D, E)

Material examined: only one empty shell was found in the sample VE04 GA-AT110 at 110-111 m.

Brachystomia carrozzai (van Aartsen, 1987) (Fig. 38B)

Material examined: one empty broken shell in the sample SE/08 DRN-7C at 581-566 m, probably swept by currents away from the coast.

Megastomia conspicua (Alder, 1850) (Fig. 38F, G)

Material examined: 2 empty shells in the sample VE/04 GA-AT-110 at 110-111 m depth.

Eulimella acicula (Philippi, 1836) (Fig. 39K, L)

Material examined: ten empty shells in the same sample (VE/04 GA-AT-110 at 110-111 m depth).

Tragula fenestrata (Jeffreys, 1848) (Fig. 39I, J)

Material examined: 3 empty shells in the sample DAI/03 EBS-100 at 102-103 m.

Turbonilla sp. 3 (Fig. 39A, B)

Material examined: six empty shells in the same VE/04 GA-AT-110 at 110-111 m.

Turbonilla lactea (Linnaeus, 1758) (Fig. 39C, D)

Material examined: two empty shells in the sample VE/04 GA-AT-110 at 110-111 m.

Turbonilla sp. 4 (Fig. 39E-G)

Material examined: seven empty shells in the samples DAI/03 EBS-100 and VE/04 GA-AT-100 collected in the depth range 102-111 m. These specimens somewhat resemble *Turbonilla sinuosa* (Jeffreys, 1884) originally described from the Sicily Channel, but there is so much uncertainty about that taxon that we do not venture an identification.

Pyrgiscus jeffreysii (Jeffreys, 1848) (Fig. 39H)

Material examined: three eroded and broken shells in the sample VE/04 GA-AT-110 at 110-111 m.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The pyramidellids of the northeast Atlantic coastal waters have been widely studied, However, data on deep-sea species are scarce and scattered. SYSOEV (2014), summarizing the existing literature records, reported only seven species of Pyramidellidae from deep-sea European seas living deeper than 2000 m, PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2009) and CABALLERO-HERRERA ET AL. (2023a) have recorded 29 species in South Azorean Seamounts, and ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (1999) included 13 species among the Mediterranean deep seashells. Here, among the 54 species of pyramidellids recorded in the Galician continental margin, 15 belong to genuinely deep-

water species whereas another 17 of them is considered accidental and are species usually found on the continental shelf.

Of the 54 species here studied, only 23 were found with soft parts (42%) and the remaining ones were empty shells. This is still a lot compared to seamount environments, where only a very small fraction of the catch consists of live-taken specimens (CABALLERO-HERRERA ET AL. 2023a). More than half of the species (33 of them) were found only on the continental shelf above 250 m depth, and of those, 18 are mainly littoral species represented by very few eroded shells. Some of these shells were proba-

(Right page) Figure. 37. A: *Odotomella doliolum* (Philippi, 1844) from DAI/03 EBS-100, juvenile shell (0.8 × 0.6 mm); B: *Folinella excavata* (Philippi, 1836) from VE/04 GA-AT-110 (2.4 × 1.1 mm); C: *Parthenina decussata* (Montagu, 1803) from VE/04 GA-AT-110 (1.3 × 0.7 mm); D: *Parthenina monozona* (Brusina, 1869) from VE04 GA-AT-110 (2.0 × 0.9 mm); E: *Parthenina* cf. *interstincta* (J. Adams, 1797) from SE/08 EBS-20 (1.6 × 0.7 mm); F: *Parthenina* cf. *interstincta* from VE/04 GA-AT-110 (1.2 × 0.6 mm); G: juvenile shell (0.9 × 0.5 mm) of *Parthenina* cf. *interstincta* from SE/08 EBS-100; H: *Parthenina indistincta* (Montagu, 1803) from VE/04 GA-AT-110 (1.6 × 0.8 mm); I: *Parthenina terebellum* (Philippi, 1844) from DAI/03 DRN-600 (1.6 × 0.7 mm); J: *Spiralina spiralis* (Montagu, 1803) from VE/04 GA-AT-110 (2.2 × 1.1 mm).

Figura. 37. A: *Odostomella doliolum* (Philippi, 1844) de DAI/03 EBS-100, concha juvenil (0,8 × 0,6 mm); B: *Folinella excavata* (Philippi, 1836) de VE/04 GA-AT-110 (2,4 × 1,1 mm); C: *Parthenina decussata* (Montagu, 1803) de VE/04 GA-AT-110 (1,3 × 0,7 mm); D: *Parthenina monoazona* (Brusina, 1869) de VE/04 GA-AT-110 (2,0 × 0,9 mm); E: *Parthenina cf. interstincta* (J. Adams, 1797) de SE/08 EBS-20 (1,6 × 0,7 mm); F: *Parthenina cf. interstincta* de VE/04 GA-AT-110 (1,2 × 0,6 mm); G: concha juvenil (0,9 × 0,5 mm) de *Parthenina cf. interstincta* de SE/08 EBS-100; H: *Parthenina indistincta* (Montagu, 1803) de VE/04 GA-AT-110 (1,6 × 0,8 mm); I: *Parthenina terebellum* (Philippi, 1844) de DAI/03 DRN-600 (1,6 × 0,7 mm); J: *Spiralina spiralis* (Montagu, 1803) de VE/04 GA-AT-110 (2,2 × 1,1 mm).

Figure 38. A: *Odostomia lukisii* from VE/04 GA-AT-110 (3.6 × 1.8 mm); B: *Brachystomia carrozzai* from SE/08 DRN-7C (2.1 × 1.1 mm); C: *Odostomia plicata* from VE/04 GA-AT-110 (2.3 × 1.0 mm); D, E: *Odostomia turrita* from VE04 GA-AT110, shell (1.6 × 0.9 mm) and protoconch; F, G: *Megastomia conspicua* from VE/04 GA-AT-110, shell (2.2 × 1.2 mm) and protoconch.

Figura 38. A: *Odostomia lukisii* de VE/04 GA-AT-110 (3,6 × 1,8 mm); B: *Brachystomia carrozzai* de SE/08 DRN-7C (2,1 × 1,1 mm); C: *Odostomia plicata* de VE/04 GA-AT-110 (2,3 × 1,0 mm); D, E: *Odostomia turrita* de VE04 GA-AT110, concha (1,6 × 0,9 mm) y protoconcha; F, G: *Megastomia conspicua* de VE/04 GA-AT-110, concha (2,2 × 1,2 mm) y protoconcha.

bly washed away from shallower bottoms, since 12 of them were collected in the same sample (VE/04 GA-AT-110), taken at 110-111 m depth near the coastline. The remaining 21 species were collected on the outer continental shelf and on the slope of the area sampled (Table 1), 11 of them deeper than 1000 m (*Turbonilla magnifica*, *Turbonilla hamonvillei*, *Eulimella ventricosa*, *Eulimella scillae*, *Eulimella neoattenuata*, *Eulimella* sp.1 and sp. 2, *Parthenina* aff. *brattstroemi*, *Pyr-*

gulina stefanisi, *Doliella nitens*, *Odostomia suboblunga*).

Most species appeared in low abundance, 10 of them represented by a single shell and 8 by 2 shells, while only 16 species were represented by 10 or more shells. Furthermore, 19 of the species were found in a single sample. These results demonstrate once again that only a few species are numerous and most are rare.

According to GOFAS ET AL. (2017), 133 species of Pyramidellidae were known in

(Right page) Figure 39. A, B: *Turbonilla* sp. 3 from VE/04 GA-AT-110, shell (3.4 × 1.1 mm) and protoconch; C, D: *Turbonilla lactea* from VE/04 GA-AT-110, concha (3.4 × 1.3 mm) and protoconch; E-G: *Turbonilla* sp.4 from VE/04 GA-AT-110, shells (2.2 × 0.9 and 2.1 × 0.8 mm) and protoconch; H: *Pyrgiscus jeffreysii* from VE/04 GA-AT-110, shell (4.0 × 1.7 mm); I, J: *Tragula fenestrata* from DAI/03 EBS-100, shell (1.3 × 0.5 mm) and protoconch; K, L: *Eulimella acicula* from VE/04 GA-AT-110, shell (1.3 × 0.6 mm) and protoconch.

Figura 39. A, B: *Turbonilla* sp. 3 de VE/04 GA-AT-110, concha ($3,4 \times 1,1$ mm) y protoconcha; C, D: *Turbonilla lactea* de VE/04 GA-AT-110, concha ($3,4 \times 1,3$ mm) y protoconcha; E-G: *Turbonilla* sp. 4 de VE/04 GA-AT-110, conchas ($2,2 \times 0,9$ y $2,1 \times 0,8$ mm) y protoconcha; H: *Pyrgiscus jeffreysii* de VE/04 GA-AT-110, concha ($4,0 \times 1,7$ mm); I, J: *Tragula fenestrata* de DAI/03 EBS-100, concha ($1,3 \times 0,5$ mm) y protoconcha; K, L: *Eulimella acicula* de VE/04 GA-AT-110, concha ($1,3 \times 0,6$ mm) y protoconcha.

Spanish waters until that date, of which 124 were recorded around the Iberian Peninsula and Balearic Islands while the remaining are only known from Canary Islands. Of the 54 species treated here, one is a new species, and four are recorded for the first time in Spanish waters (*Parthenina brattstroemi*, *Pyrgiscus mediocris*, *Turbonilla hamonvillei* and *Eulimella atlantis*). Of the remaining species, 7 have been only identified at a generic level and some of them may be new to science, and the other 42 were already known in the Ibero-Balearic geographical context. TRIGO ET AL. (2018) recorded 47 species of Pyramidellidae in the Galician coast, of which 19 are recorded here.

Of the 27 species recorded in the South Azorean Seamount (PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 2009; CABALLERO-HERRERA ET AL., 2023a), only five were found in the area here studied: *Parthenina flexuosa*, *Eulimella neoattenuata*, *E. atlantis*, *Turbonilla hamonvillei* and *Pyrgiscus mediocris*, therefore documenting a broad range in the North Atlantic. The known distribution area of the following 13 species is expanded to include the North Atlantic demarcation of Spanish waters: *Tiberia minuscula*, *Doliella nitens*, *Liostomia hansgei*, *Liostomia afzelii*, *Odosstomia suboblonga*, *Pyrgulina stefanisi*, *Parthenina* cf. *palazzii*, *Eulimella scillae*, *Eulimella neoattenuata*, *Eulimella ventricosa*, *Eulimella* cf. *atkinsi*, *Turbonilla multilirata*, *Odosstomella doliolum*.

It is noteworthy that most of the species (40) here recorded in the continental shelf and slope of Galicia are also known in the Mediterranean. However the variability of some species with a wide geographic distribution should be reviewed, and could mask complexes of

different species. This is the case of some species for which their presence has been reported from the Atlantic coasts of northern Europe south to Angola, including the Mediterranean (i.e. *Megastomia conoidea*, *Brachystomia eulimoides*, *B. scalaris*, *Odosstomia turrita*, *O. acuta*, *O. unidentata*, *Liostomia clavula*, *Parthenina interstincta* or *Eulimella ventricosa*). Although the European and West African pyramidellids have been the subject of numerous taxonomic studies, the status of several species must still be subject to a thorough review through integrative taxonomy, combining morphology and genetic tools.

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